

Early Books 1470-1501

Fascicule XXX

James Gray Bookseller

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Printers for XXX

Basel

Wenssler XI

Amerbach # VIII, XV, XXII

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Johann Pruss, XVII

Cologne

Ulrich Zel, XVIII

Ulm

Johann Zainer, XII, XVI

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LYONS

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Magdenburg

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Rome

Freitag XXI

With tooling signed by Nicolaus Seman of Erfurt

I 437J **Saint Augustine, Aurelius.**

De civitate Dei. (Sente[n]tia beati Augustini episcopi ex libro retractat[i]onum ip[s]ius de libris) Title on leaf [3]r: Aurelij Augustini Ipponensis e[pi]sco[pi] doctoris eximij de ciuitate Dei [con]tra paganos liber p[ri]mus incipit: Aurelii Augustini Ipponensis episcopi doctoris eximii de civitate Dei contra paganos liber primus incipit: De civitate Dei contra paganos

Basel: Michael Wenssler [and Bernhard Richel] March 25, 1479. Price: \$25,000

Super Median Folio: 450 X 340 mm. No signatures: [1³⁻¹⁰ 2-6¹⁰ 7-10⁸ 11⁶ 12-15^{10/8} 16⁸ 17-18¹⁰ 19-21⁸ 22¹⁰ 23⁸ 24-25⁶ 26¹⁰ 27⁸ 28⁶ 29³. • [Lacking leaves 1, 2 & 294] 245] (of 248) leaves.

This copy is bound in its original blind stamped pigskin over wooden boards. **With tooling signed by Nicolaus Seman of Erfurt (active around 1460-1486 in Erfurt and Würzburg)** He was a goldsmith, bookbinder, type cutter.? Thieme-Becker XXX, 484. The tool with the binders name is used twice on the front board, and four times on the back cover with four other individual stamps (original brass fittings and clasps were removed)

Textus sancti Augustini de ciuitate dei Basilee impressus Explicit feliciter. Anno .lxxix.

First colophon (fol. [190]r) Printed in red with double coat of arms.

Textus sancti

Augustini de ciuitate di Basilee impressus. Explicit feliciter. Anno .lxxix.

On leaf [191]r: Sacre pagine p[ro]fesso[r]um Ordinis P[rae]dicatorum Thome Valois et Nicolai Triueth i[n] libros beati Augustini de ciuitate Dei comentari feliciter inchoant. Second colophon (fol. [248]v):" M et cccclxxix vij K[a]ll[endas] Aprilis opero se est consummatum"

This is the first Basel printing of **The City of God** by Augustine with the commentary by Thomas Waleys and Nicolaus Trivet . ¶ Michael Wenssler was born in Strasbourg, moved to Basel at an early age and quickly became a prominent typographer and printer. His earliest work, is dated to 1472 and was one of the first books printed in Basel. Wenssler stayed in Basel until 1491. Wenssler and Richel collaborated on this printing project using a type font they jointly owned.

¶The City of God is St. Augustine's fifth century response to assertions that Christianity had caused the decline of Rome.

De ciuitate Dei contra paganos is divided into 22 books. The first 10 refute the claims to divine power of various pagan communities. The last 12 retell the biblical story of mankind from Genesis to the Last Judgment, offering what Augustine presents as the true history of the City of God against which, and only against which, the history of the City of Man, including the history of Rome, can be properly understood. This Book remains impressive as a whole and fascinating in its parts. The stinging attack on

paganism in the first books is memorable and effective, the encounter with Platonism in books 8-10 is of great philosophical significance, and the last books (especially book 19, with a vision of true peace) offer a view of human destiny that would be widely persuasive for at least a thousand years. In a way, Augustine's City of God is (even consciously) the Christian rejoinder to Plato's Republic and Cicero's imitation of Plato, his own Republic. City of God would be read in various ways throughout the Middle Ages, at some points virtually as a founding document for a political order of kings and popes that Augustine could hardly have imagined. At its heart is a powerful contrarian vision of human life, one which accepts the place of disaster, death, and disappointment while holding out hope of a better life to come, a hope that in turn eases and gives direction to life in this world. Augustine is remarkable for what he did, more than five million words of his writings survive, virtually all displaying the strength and sharpness of his mind and some possessing the rare power to attract and hold the attention of readers in both his day and ours. His distinctive theological style shaped Latin Christianity in a way surpassed only by scripture itself." (Encyclopedia Britannica 11th edition)

"Augustine's complicated personal journey has enriched his thought with a large number of themes and starting points, which may not have found a definitive systematic placement but precisely for this reason exercise all the greater a fascination upon those periods that, like the present, shun naively integral constructions. A schoolteacher, he was brought up on texts of the classical period, and from these he got to know the best products of Greek and Latin culture." (Gian Biagio Conte).

ISTC **ia01241000**: <https://data.cerl.org/istc/ia01241000> Goff A1241 : BMC III 726 & 738: Hain-Copinger 2058: Pell 1556: CIBN A-685: Girard 39: IBP 631: SI 419: Sajtó-Soltész 375: Coll(U) 185: Coll(S) 117: Madsen 399: GW 2885: Bod-inc A-527: Sheppard 2338: Pr 7489-7534:

This image is an unfinished outline for the Lombard Initial Q, an illuminator has dry pointed an outline, which continues below the photo, I feel it is uncommon as I haven't had a book with one of these before.

Here is a hand supplied Maiblumen initial, which shows a relaxed and complicated style. There are a couple of other initials supplied like this, as well as a few filled with faces, and a coat of arms on the first leaf.

Sacre pagine p̄fessor̄ ordinis p̄dicatorū
 Thome valois ꝛ nicolai triueth ī libros be
 ati augustinī de ciuitate dei Comentar̄ia fe
 liciter inchoant.

Luminis impetus letificat cui
 tatem dei. In ps̄. fons sapiētie
 verbum dei residens in excelis
 p̄ dona sua p̄cedens in quatu
 or capita se diuisit. scz in qua
 tuor flumina. de quibz scribit̄
 eccl̄iastic̄. xxiii. Ego sapientia
 effudi flumina dū mentibus q̄

tuor doctor̄ eccl̄ie. quibus specialiter in expoſitōe
 sacre scripture stulit p̄ncipatum copiosissime aquas
 sapientie salutaris infudit. quas tñ mirabili dispositi
 onibus distribuit. Quibus et anthonom̄ice per

pt 13 liba de civitate

Ex libris Michaelis Davanzoli Bibliothecarii
Anno 1741

Aurelij augustini ipponensis epi doctores et
m de civitate dei otra paganos liber primus
incipit

Capitulum

Cosiosissima civitatem dei hinc in hoc tepoz cursu cuz inter implos pegnnae ex fide vivens hinc i illa stabilitate sedis eterne qua nunc exspectat p paciam quo ad usqz iusticia ouertatur in iudicij demiceps ad eptura p excellensiam vitoria vltima t pace pfecta bocope a te mstruio et mea pmissiore debito desere aduerlus eos qui odiorici9 deos suos pferunt fili caustissime marcelline suscepi. Magnun op9 et arduu sed deo adiuco no ster eam scio quib9 virib9 opus sit vt psuadeat supbis quata sit virtus bulitatis qua fit vt omnia terrena cacumina tpali mobilitate nutantia no humano vsurpato fastus9 diuina gratia donata celsitudo et ascendat. Rex em9 obitoe civitatis hui9 ve qua loc institutum in scriptura ipi sicut iudicij dinc legis apuie qua didit est deus supbis sstiter bulib9 aut dar gnam hoc vero qd dei est supbe qz aie spuz mstratus a fectat amatqz sibi in laudib9 dicere subiectis er detellare supbos. Vn etia9 terrena civitate que cu dnan appetit et si ppli seruiat ipa ei dnandi libido dnat no est ptercumbi siletio quicqd dicere suscepit hui9 opis ro postulat facultas dat. Ex hac namqz existunt inimici aduerlus quos defendenda dei civitas est. Quoz tm multi correcio impietatis erroze cuos in ea snt satis idonei multi vero in eam caris exarbedunt ignibus odioz tamqz manifestis busi cija red epa totis eius igrati snt vt hodie otra cu signas non moueret miserz hostili fugietes in sctis eius locis vita de qua supbiue hinc mrent. An non t illi romani xpi noi mfecti snt quib9 ppter xpm barbari peccerunt. Testant bec martiz loca et basilice apostoloz q i vastatione v biz ad se ofugietes suos alienos q ceperunt spucuz qz se iuebat inimic9 ibi ac ciebat limitē trucidatoris furo. illo ductatur a miseratib9 hostib9 qbus etia9 extra ipa loca peccerat ne in eos incurreret qui simile miscdia no bebant. Qui tm etiam ipsi alibi truces atqz hostili moze seuictes postea qm ab loca illa venieb9 vbi fuerat mcreditu9 g alibi belli fure iuculisset tota feniedi refrenatur immantat t captiuadi cupiditas fragebatur. Sic euaserunt multi qui nunc xpianis tpiibus detrahut mala q illa civitas prulit xpo impucae. Sona vero que in eos vt viuere

rent ppter xpi honore facta sunt no impucae xpo noit rois fato suo cu potu debent si qd recte sapent illa q ab hostib9 aspa t dura p pessi snt illi bine pudentie tribu9 que solet eoz ppos hosti mozes bellis emedare atqz oterere itaqz vita moze aliu iustia atqz lauda bilē talib9 afflictoib9 exerce pbatqz vel in melioza t caltere vt in bns adbuictis xpi vsus alios det me. Illud vero ostendendum qd eis vbi cuqz ppter xpi nome vt in locis xpi ro mini dicatimms t amplissimis ac plazioze misericdia ad capacitate multitudine cedis pteer be loz moze eruculci barbari peccerunt. hoc eritib9 tpiibus xpianis hinc deo ags gratias hinc ad cu9 nomi veracit curri vt effugi ant penas ignis et i mscqd nome multi ceptuz mendaciter vsurparunt vt effugeret penas pntis exiti9 Nam quos videt petulant t pro caqter inultate seruus xpi sunt in bns plimi qd illum mteritū elab qz9 no eu asissent mstruos xpi se ee similia int. Et nunc in grata superbia atqz impiissima infamia eius noi te sstine cois de puer so vt sempiternis tenebris puniatur ad qd nome ore ut subdolo ofuguerit vt tpali luce fruerent.

T De bella gesta de septa snt vt an cobi tam roma ul ab al exozu imperio legat t pferat sic ab altemis emia alic qua capti ee civitate vt hostes qui ceperat pacerit eis quos ad teoz suoz tpla consu gisse opererat aut aliqui ducē barbarz pcepisse vt irupto opid nulluz ferret qm in illo vt illo teplo fuisset inuect. Nonne vidit encas pamu p aras sed ante sanguis quos ipse facta uerat ignes. Nonne diomedes et vlixes eess summe custodib9 arcis corripere facta effigiem m ambub9 eructu virginas ausi bue ontinge viteras. Nec tm qd sequit vez est ex illo fluē ac fero sublapa t ferri spes d animum. Postea qpe vicerit postea troia fero ignibus q delevit postea ofugietē at arā prima mun oberticauer. Mec io troia perit q mbingrua pdit. Quid em plus ipa mnerua perbiderat vt piretur. An forte custodes suos hoc sane vez est. Illis qpe interceptis pocuit auferri thez emibotes a simulacro h simulacuz a custodib9 seruabat. Hūo g colebat vt patia custodiret t cuos q suos n valuit custodire custodes.

Cece qualib9 dms vire romani panti dā se omē alle gaudēbant nimii mserabile erroze. Et nobis succentent cu be dms eoz talia didim9 cu nec succēfent auctozib9 suis quos vt edillitē mercede be derit. t dōz est9 ipos insup et salario publico t bonozib9 dignissimos habuerit. Nepe

Lib. 1. transverso
1741-1742 P.D.

Some of Nicholas Seman's tools.

II

284J Gualtherus Burlaeus.and Aristotle (Walter Burley (c. 1275–1344/5)

Expositio Gualteri Burlei super decem Libros Ethicorum Aristotelis (Contains the text of Robert Grosseteste's translation of the Nicomachean Ethics)

Venice: Simon de Luere for Andreas Torresanus, 4 Sept 1500. Price: \$12,500

Super Chancery Folio 31 x 21 cm. A⁸ a⁶ b-x⁸ y¹⁰. Second edition after that of 1481. This copy is bound in contemporary 1/4 blind-tooled goatskin over wooden boards with 3 (of 4) metal catches on front cover, rebaced retaining most of original backstrip, conspicuous termite damage on front cover, rear cover replaced with modern board, endpapers renewed; contents washed with residual soiling on opening leaves, worming through much of volume generally not impairing legibility, crude restoration in blank margins at beginning and end, with small wood cut diagrams throughout.

This edition contains the *Ethica Nicomachea*, Books 1-10, in the Latin translation of Robertus Grosseteste (1175-1253), incipit "[O]mnis ars et om[n]is doctrina similiter aut[em] [et] actus [et] electio bonum quoddam ap=pete[re] videt[ur]. [de]o b[e]n[e] enunciaueru[n]t bonu[m] q[uo]d omnia appetu[n]t", b1r-y9v; colophon (Venetijs impresse arte Simonis de Leure: impensis v[ir]o domini Andree Torresani de Asula. Anno M.D. die v[er]o, III. Septeb[er]is.),

Typical for these early commentaries is the interpretation of Aristotle's doctrine in the light of Christian religion. In 1246/1248, Robert Grosseteste achieved a complete translation of the *Nicomachean Ethics*. The first to write commentaries on it were Albert the Great (twice) and Thomas Aquinas. Both attempted to interpret Aristotle philosophically, avoiding the theological implications. Burley turned to moral philosophy and *varia* rather late in his life, completing his exposition of Aristotle's *Ethics* in 1333–1334 and of the *Politics* in 1340–1343.

¶There are two printed editions of this work, the one offered here is the second, the first is quite rare-Goff B 1300, (3 copies) Harvard, St Bonaventure Univ. and University of Penn.

¶The copy offered today is also rare- Goff B1301 (3 copies) Free Library of Philadelphia, Newberry, U. of Illinois.

Goff; B-1301 ; BM 15th cent.,; V, 576 (IB. 24667); GW; 5779; ; Hain-Copinger; *4144; Harman; 191; ISTC (online); ib01301000; Proctor; 5269; Pellechet; 3080

Canon Sacratissi

me misse. vna cum expositione eiusdem. vbi
in primis premititur pulera contemplatio
ante missam habenda de cristi pulcritudine
Et quomodo ipsa in sua passione ab eo oino fuerat ablata
Qualiterq; quilibet celebrans debeat esse dispositus. In
cipit foeliciter.

Instrumenta vbi offeratur altare

In y fannen
In y aduocatus vnd y lotz veractes
In y yllze bedarft mit gntz tuch vor dem altar dor off y lieg
In y pfunde sal wasser dieß gabel vff tisch
In y ynnen pfundel von pfunden dor ein man das geylde tegut
In y vorgelet eten topfgen dor ein man das geylde tegut
In y pfunde wasser do mit man das topfgen vor macht
In y v allen Ordelstetzer tegut vber die geylde
In y v allen Ordelstetzer tegut dem bischoff vmb die grünen
In y sal vnd bristen do der bischoff vff set
In y quechel do an man das darbyet
In y pecken vnd gantze dor neben
In y nussen kolben
In y mulden mit asthen
In y nusse pfundel mit salz
In y ledige fruhgere pfundel dor neben
In y mulden mit kalte
In y pfundel gamer | kelley | portz gessel pen
In y noch noch
In y v allen abetung dor von man die teugndige vff die ka
In y lieg vff altare p | von ein pfund
In y alt tuch do mit man den altar vffset
In y besen do mit man den altar beset
In y flage bey dem altare
In y tuch vff den altare die bedeken

III. 466J Balthasar de Porta (fl. 1487- 1499)

Expositio Canonis Missae. (Canon sacratissime misse: unacum expositione eiusdem: ubi in primis premitit pulchra contemplatio ante missam habenda de christi pulcritudine. Et quo mo[*d*]o ipsa in sua passione: ab eo o[*mn*]ino fuerat ablata. Qualiterque quilibet celebrans debeat esse dispositus incipit foeliciter.)

[Leipzig : Gregorius Böttiger (aka Werman), about 1495. Price: \$16,000 Chancery half-sheet Quarto: 18.5 x12.5 cm. Signatures: aa-dd⁶, 24 of 24 leaves. Editio princeps, text in gothic letter, including a set of large caps, large woodcut initial and display face on title page, long list in a contemporary hand beneath printed title; This copy is bound in antique parchment .

Balthasar de Porta's Canon Missae, also contains the the proposal of the Exposition of the Eucharist before the celebration of mass . This commentary on the Mass, has verses taken from the Jesuida of Hieronymus de Vallibus, which are used in the appropriate context to illustrate or emphasize the author's meaning. We know very few facts about the life of Balthasar de Porta , a Cistercian monk who served as Provisor at the order's College (Saint Bernard) at Leipzig until about 1499. In the same years, he also published another work about Mass, the Expositio mysteriorum missae (Leipzig: Kacheloven, 1494) and a work on the heretical Bohemian Brethren, Conclusiones contra quorundam Bohemorum errores (Lepzig: Böttiger, about 1494), in which Balthasar refutes specific "errors" of the Hussite beliefs. Balthasar de Porta was Provisor of the Cistercian College of St. Bernhard in Leipzig (fl. 1487-1499).

Goff B39; H 2345*; GfT GfT: Gesellschaft für Typenkunde des XV. Jahrhunderts. Veröffentlichungen. 33 parts. Leipzig [etc], 1907-39. 521, 522; Pell 1753; BSB-Ink B-25; GW 3216; ISTC ib00039000.

US copies: Huntington Library (2), Southern Methodist Univ, Yale University
<https://data.cerl.org/istc/ib00039000>

617•678•4517

IV 335J Bible: Saint Jerome, Gabriello Bruno (active 1480-1514.)**Biblia cum summariis concordantiis : diuisionibus: quattuor repertoriis p[ro]positis: numeri[ue] foliorum****distinctione: terse et fidelit[er] imp[re]ssa.**

Lyons: Jean Pivard, 29 Jan. 1500 & 1. Impresserunt aute[m] solertes viri Franciscus Fradin et Ioha[n]nes Piuard socij impre, 1500. Price: \$15,000.

Folio 27 x 19 cm: ♂⁸ ♀⁸, a⁸ b⁶, c-z⁸ A-Z⁸ Aa⁸ Bb⁸; aa-cc⁸ dd¹⁰. Bound in original full calf over wooden boards with 10 brass bosses.

This Bible also includes the "Tabula alphabetica" of Gabriel Bruno, and notes on "translatores ... Biblie", and "mzaodi intelligendi ... scripturam"; at the end, "Interpretationes nominum hebraycorum"; with marginal references.

&¹r [Title-page.] &1v [Pivard, Jean: Introductory letter addressed to the reader.] Incipit: 'Ne nesciens et ob id ingratus sacrosanctam diuini verbi . . .' &1v 'Pulchra et vtilis diuisio totius Biblie'. &1v 'In tabulam primam de ordine librorum ad lectorem disticon'. Incipit: 'Perspice nunc, lector, quis debitus ordo librorum'; 1 distich.

&1v 'Prima quattuor tabulorum'. &2v 'Tabula secunda continens libros Biblie per ordinem alphabeti'. &2v [Alexander de Villa Dei pseudo-]: 'Tertia tabula'. Pref. no. 58. [con]1r Brunus, Gabriel: 'Quarta tabula'.

ç 8r [Explanatory note about translators of the Bible and commentators.]

ç 8v 'Modi intelligendi sacram scripturam'. a2r Hieronymus: [Letter addressed to] Paulinus [ep. 53]. 'Prologus in Bibliam'.. On this edition see also Hillard, 'Les éditions de la Bible', 72-3.

Goff B604; HC 3128; GfT 1883, 1884; Pell 2341; CIBN B-426; Arnoult 288; Girard 108; Parguez 213; Polain(B) 4210; IBE 1040; SI 764;

**Sancti thome de aquino super li
bris Boecii de consolatione philoso
phie cōmentum cum expositione feli
citer incipit.**

Philosophie feruam oportet ut tibi contingat vera libertas.
Hec sunt vbi seruat octava ep̄la ad Lucillū. q̄ vocat̄ p̄bi
lolephā sciam veniat recte le b̄se. sc̄to met̄bapt̄lice. & p̄bi
lolephā asert̄ delectatione mirabilem firmitate & puritate. ex
deco tribuor. Et mult̄ vlt̄a est p̄bia vera in abili & vltima ex
de celo & m̄do ar̄s̄ouit. Et n̄ulla sc̄a m̄s̄o est p̄bie que
clarificat̄ animā & facit̄ delectari eā in s̄ seculo in p̄sente & recedat̄. ex lib̄o s̄ po
mo & monte. Et p̄bia trahit̄ hoīem ab occupat̄e ignominie ad sciam. & tenet̄ sul
tate ad lucē sapie & ad claritatē intellect̄. ex codē lib̄o Boet̄ice. Et q̄ p̄bia a sa
pientiē liberat̄ metu. meos nō orn̄bat̄ s̄m Lucillū in lib̄o de cons̄ol̄atione. & m̄s̄o p̄
Boet̄ Seneca has & p̄m̄s̄o p̄m̄s̄o & effect̄ laudabilem p̄bie merito. beatit̄
nos ad suā p̄bie in p̄p̄s̄ie p̄p̄s̄ie sic n̄s̄o. p̄bie feruam oportet. Que qui
v̄t̄ p̄p̄s̄ie p̄t̄. p̄biā mult̄a r̄s̄us̄. s̄mo sic. Illi q̄ feruere p̄t̄. s̄r̄uente d̄el̄ cō
tigit̄ vera libertas. h̄ p̄bia est h̄m̄s̄. s̄m̄. s̄biōs̄ nota q̄ libertas est nob̄ill̄s̄ima cō
ditio quā n̄ humana cōsiderat̄ & affectat̄. s̄biōs̄ p̄ p̄. unde Seneca qui postquā
s̄m̄s̄ p̄p̄s̄ie d̄el̄. hoc est. s̄p̄m̄ s̄r̄uere p̄bie libertas est. p̄p̄s̄ie sic. Illi q̄ s̄r̄uere
q̄s̄ anim̄ p̄s̄it̄. v̄s̄a d̄is̄p̄s̄ie. ac̄t̄o reḡ. aḡa & ob̄t̄it̄. d̄a d̄em̄s̄it̄. & sic q̄
nemo est s̄cur̄. p̄bia est h̄m̄s̄. s̄m̄. s̄biōs̄ nota n̄a s̄r̄uere sunt de p̄s̄e
bois̄. s̄biōs̄ declarat̄ p̄ Seneca. r̄s̄. ep̄la ad Lucillū loquū de p̄bia r̄s̄o. Hec
ait̄ s̄m̄s̄ & fabricat̄. quā d̄p̄s̄ie. ac̄t̄o reḡ. & ob̄t̄it̄. d̄a d̄em̄s̄it̄. sed̄ ad ca
dem̄s̄it̄ er̄s̄it̄. s̄m̄s̄it̄ d̄ir̄iḡt̄ carit̄. h̄ s̄ne h̄c n̄s̄o ē s̄cur̄. p̄p̄s̄ie s̄r̄uere
sic. Illi est̄ s̄m̄s̄it̄. q̄s̄ m̄s̄it̄ cognitiōni vlt̄im̄i s̄m̄s̄ magn̄i increment̄. p̄bia est̄ bu
s̄m̄s̄. s̄m̄. s̄biōs̄ nota q̄ cognitiō vlt̄im̄i s̄m̄s̄ magn̄i increment̄. p̄s̄it̄ ad v̄
t̄. ex s̄r̄o. s̄biōs̄ declarat̄. N̄a s̄m̄s̄it̄. s̄m̄s̄it̄ v̄t̄e h̄iane est̄ h̄m̄s̄o cū cogni
t̄ōn̄ p̄bia r̄s̄it̄. H̄m̄s̄it̄. p̄bia in tertio de p̄s̄e p̄s̄ie p̄ s̄m̄s̄o q̄ s̄m̄s̄o ē s̄r̄uere
ōm̄ d̄em̄s̄it̄. s̄m̄s̄it̄ p̄s̄it̄. Et i codē s̄o d̄m̄s̄it̄ p̄bia in q̄ s̄r̄uere v̄t̄e h̄iane d̄
q̄s̄ ad eā p̄s̄it̄. p̄p̄s̄ie s̄r̄uere. Illi q̄ s̄r̄uere q̄s̄ s̄r̄uere h̄m̄s̄o p̄s̄ie d̄em̄s̄it̄. h̄
h̄m̄s̄. s̄m̄. s̄biōs̄ nota de s̄. s̄biōs̄ nota q̄ s̄r̄uere h̄m̄s̄o p̄s̄ie d̄em̄s̄it̄. h̄
Hoc n̄a s̄m̄s̄it̄ p̄bia p̄s̄it̄ v̄t̄e p̄s̄ie d̄em̄s̄it̄. p̄p̄s̄ie s̄r̄uere. Illi est̄ s̄m̄s̄it̄
q̄s̄ est̄ maḡistra oīm sc̄larū. n̄s̄it̄ oīm virtūū. s̄m̄s̄it̄ solat̄. s̄m̄s̄it̄. q̄s̄
est̄ pacat̄i v̄t̄e h̄iane & cultū er̄b̄ot̄ano est̄ recta s̄i ant̄e v̄t̄e h̄iane. p̄s̄ie
lophā est̄ h̄m̄s̄. s̄m̄. s̄biōs̄ nota q̄ s̄r̄uere h̄m̄s̄o p̄s̄ie d̄em̄s̄it̄. h̄
alici s̄m̄s̄it̄. s̄biōs̄ declarat̄. n̄a p̄bia est̄ maḡistra oīm virtūū. s̄m̄s̄it̄ de p̄s̄e
p̄s̄ie tertio. p̄bia est̄ n̄s̄it̄ oīm virtūū d̄em̄s̄it̄. p̄s̄ie s̄r̄uere. p̄bia est̄ h̄m̄s̄o
s̄m̄s̄it̄. s̄m̄s̄it̄. q̄s̄ est̄ p̄s̄ie v̄t̄e h̄iane. q̄s̄ est̄

Boethius, Anicius Manlius Torquatus Severinus (480-524)

Sancti thome de aquino super libris Boecii de consolatione philosophie co[m]mentum
cum expositione feliciter incipit.

Lyons: Guillaume le Roy, 1484 (not after 24 December 1484). Price: \$20,000.

Chancery folio (296 x 210mm). signatures :a-x⁸ (a¹ & x⁸ blank); Part I only, 166 leaves (of 168, without first and last blanks). Red initial with blue flourishing, smaller red and blue ink initials, red and blue paragraph marks (some leaves browned, repaired tear in text of one leaf, some dampstains). The text surrounded by commentary ascribed to Thomas Aquinas. Le Roy was the first printer in Lyons and began printing in 1473. Bound in Contemporary blind tooled morocco, remains of paper label on rear board (lacking clasps, losses to leather, rebacked preserving some original leather).

Boethius became the connecting link between the logical and metaphysical science of antiquity and the scientific attempts of the Middle Ages. His influence on medieval thought was still greater through his *De consolazione philosophiae*. Whether Boethius was a Christian has been doubted Nevertheless, for a long time the book was read with the greatest reverence by all Christendom, and its author was regarded as a martyr for the true faith" (Schaff-Herzog). ¶ In this prosimetrical apocalyptic dialogue, Boethius our narrator encounters Lady-Philosophy , who appears in his time of need, the muse of poetry has in short failed him. Philosophy adresses among great protest Boethius' bad interpretations and misunderstandings of fate and free will....

One thousand five hundred years later It is still fair to ask, the same questions which Boethius asks .. "Why do bad things happen to good people?"

And Philosophy answers: "The judgment of most people is based not on the merits of a case but on the fortune of its outcome; they think that only things which turn out happily are good." "You have merely discovered the two-faced nature of this blind goddess [Fortune] ... For now she has deserted you, and no man can ever be secure until he has been deserted by Fortune."

¶ "I [Fortune] spin my wheel and find pleasure in raising the low to a high place and lowering those who were on top. Go up, if you like, but only on condition that you will not feel abused when my sport requires your fall."

This copy was released/issued without the Pseudo-Boethian *De disciplina scholarium* from the same press printed later, which usually accompanies it.

ISTC ib00779000.; Goff; B779; GW; 4535; Walsh, 3737;Hain-Copinger; 3418; Copinger; 1107.

Copies in United States: Harvard (I) Gordon W. Jones, M.D., (I) Yale (I)

VI 277J Eusebius (c. 260-c. 340)

Eusebius Pa[m]phili de eua[n]gelica preparac[i]o[n]e ex greco in latinu[m] translatus Incipit feliciter.

[Cologne, Ulrich Zel, not after 1473]. Price. \$19,000

Chancery folio 29 x21 cm. Signatures: [a]¹², [b-o]¹⁰, [p]⁸. This copy is bound in new quarter calf over original wooden boards. Capitals supplied in Red and Blue. The copy at the Vienna Schottenstift has rubricator's date 1473 (Hübl) .

Ulrich Zel, Cologne's first printer, learned his craft from Fust and Schoeffer in Mainz. He began printing in Cologne probably in 1465. , This is one of the earliest editions of this work, most likely the Second, (editio princeps: Venice 1470).

The purpose of this work is "to justify the Christian in rejecting the religion and philosophy of the Greeks in favor of that of the Hebrews, and then to justify him in not observing the Jewish manner of life ."

The following summary of its contents is taken from Mr. Gifford's introduction to his translation of the "Praeparatio: ¶ The first three books discuss the threefold system of Pagan Theology: Mythical, Allegorical, and Political. The next three, IV-VI, give an account of the chief oracles, of the worship of demons, and of the various opinions of Greek Philosophers on the doctrines of Fate and Free Will. Books VII-IX give reasons for preferring the religion of the Hebrews founded chiefly on the testimony of various authors to the excellency of their Scriptures and the truth of their history. In Books X-XII Eusebius argues that the Greeks had borrowed from the older theology and philosophy of the Hebrews, dwelling especially on the supposed dependence of Plato upon Moses. In the the last three books, the comparison of Moses with Plato is continued, and the mutual contradictions of other Greek Philosophers, especially the Peripatetics and Stoics, are exposed and criticized."

The "Praeparatio" is a gigantic feat of erudition, and according to Harnack (Chronologie, II, p. 120), was, like many of Eusebius' other works, actually composed during the stress of the persecution. It ranks, with the Chronicle, second only to the Church History in importance, because of its copious extracts from ancient authors, whose works have perished." (CE)

ISTC ie00119000; Goff E119; HC(Add)R 6698; GfT 122; Voull(K) 402; Pell 4641 & 4641A (var); Hillard 780; Fernillot 229; IGI 3755; IBP 2096; Madsen 1525, 1526; Hübl 183; Ernst(Hildesheim) II,III 58; Finger 368, 369; Borm 981; Voull(B) 670; Voull(Trier) 325; Günt(L) 914; Döring-Fuchs E-36, E-37; Bod-inc E-048; Sheppard 678, 679; Rhodes(Oxford Colleges) 745;GW 9441.

Quom enim inquit iamis su-
perstitio inuicem cepit quasi
maloz omnium fons in-
stitudinem deoz constituit. quibus
hostias imolare solēnia facere si-
mulacra statuere et tēpla cōde-
re permissit. quā tamē deoz sepul-
cra prius fuerit et magificēt? cō-
dita tēploz appellacōe uocata
sunt. Et apud Larisē ciuita-
tē Acrisij sepulcrū ē. quō inō sa-
crarij loco uenerantur. et in arce
athēnēsi ut Antiochus in nouo
historiaz scripsit Cecropos se-
pulcrū fuit. In tēplo uero Dalla-
dis: quā ciuitē appellant Erich-
thom? iacet. In mar? autē Cumol-
priatq; Daire filij? i eleusine vna
cum Celei filiabus sepultus est
Quid istas? non enī latet a gen-
tibus sepulcra hominū adorari.
Hec quidem Clemēs.

Nos autē rursus alij? hęc
repetētes dicere nō du-
bitam? natūa in o uero
simē? omnibus esse hominibus? in-
situm nō solum utiq; quid atq;
oducibile dei noie significari. uerū
etiā omnium rez creatorem sic
appellari. et uero quēdem ita om-
nes natura duce conueniunt. re-
autē creaturas p creatore colue-
rūt pter unū aut admodū pau-
cos ut uerissimis hebreoz libri
ōnditur. quā rebus uisibilibus
ad intelligibilia mentis oculos
sanctē reducētes non creature

aliquos ipsi rez oim creatōi cū
etorumq; largitōi honorum dei
appellacōem attribuerūt. Ceteri
autē omnes tenebris animi uo-
luti ad tātam impietate deducti
fūt ut pcedū more honestū ac
cōducibile honoz q; oim exte-
mū uoluptate corpis tezmiazēt
et hac ratiōe eos quē uoluptatem
adinuenerūt genera uel auerūt
atq; āplificāre maleficos et mō-
les viros ut dictū est quē honoz
lāgitores saluatores et deos ap-
pellarunt. piam hui? nominis
notionem natura eis inuitā ad
eos transferētes quis honorū
uentozes putabant. tantumq;
mētis insania ualuit ut nec pec-
care se arbitrāretur nec erubescē-
rēt diuinis honoribus maleficol
atq; potentes homines ppe reg-
na tunc primū cōstitutā colere
atq; admirari. Quomq; ut iam
dixim? mores hominū legibus
stabiliti nō essent: nec suplicia
peccatoibus imminerēt. aduicia
nefanda mat: in omnia: maribus
ereptam pudicitiam: homicidia
patriicia: confecta scelere bella
quasi res pulcherrime gestas
dijs suis attribuebāt et earum
rerum memoriam posteri oib?
quasi perutilem rlinquere stude-
bant.

Nec theologia pisorū
fuit. quā iunioris natū
talū rez sciētia nō paz

ET...

Lauacrum couren
cie omnibus sacer
dotibus pezutile

VII. 448J Jacobus de Gruytrode

Lavacrum concienie [sic] omnibus sacerdotibus perutile

Lyptzck [Leipzig] : Gregor Böttiger, 1495. \$18,000

Quarto: 12 x 9 cm. Signatures: a⁸ b-p⁶ q⁸. [Errors in foliation: lxxxviii-xcviii foliated xc-xcviii, with xc as cxi, xciii as cxv] Blank initial spaces. f Bound in half leather of the 19th century, with quite a lot of contemporary marginalia, on nearly every page. "In 1492 Böttiger along with Arnold of Cologne issued their first book" [Rush Hawkins and Alfred Pollard 1910]

This "Soap (or Baptism?) of the Conscience" is filled with morally instructive stories intended to keep priests faithful to their vows and safe from worldly temptations, lest they suffer the "harshesht punishments" of hell. In this work he tries in numerous moral and instructive stories to prove the nullity of worldly joys. Born in Gruitrode ca. 1400-10, Jacobus van Eertwach was a Carthusian monk who served as an abbot of the prior of the Liege from 1440 until his death in 1475, during which time he produced numerous works of spiritual guidance for both clergy and laypersons. "Lavacrum" was first printed by Anton Sorg in 1489.

This is a treatise against immorality, especially the priests, which was first published in Nuremberg around 1488.

ISTC il00099000; Goff L99; IBP 3382; Madsen 2157; Voull(B) 1383; Günt(L) 1205; Hubay(Würzburg) 1187; Pad-Ink 375; Wilhelmi 387; BSB-Ink L-71.050; GW 13880. Not in Hain, BMC, STC et c.<https://data.cerl.org/istc/il00099000> Copies; United States of America 1) Library of Congress 2) Univ. of California, Law Library.

De sacramto cohabitatio supra scripto ad indignos p[ro]p[ri]os de ordine p[ro]p[ri]os

Solum ^{ambrosij cui indy^o sunt missy lxxxviii}
 exponit beatus Ambrosius dicens. Qui indigne christum sumit
 item est ac si ipsum interficeret. Augustinus ait. Indignus sacer-
 dos ut est concubiniarius, symoniacus, proprietarius, ebri-
 sus etc. quot verba in canone recitat, toties in faciem salua-
 toris spuit, dum illum leuat tunc impio pugno verberat, dum
 dividit crucifigit, dum vero sumit in cloaca mundissimi et in-
 dignissimi corporis sui picit. Decille. Quia pro Scor^o de Mis-
 sa boni sacerdotis infinite melior est quam missa mali sacerdo-
 tis quamvis sacrificium utrobique sit equale. Ob hoc audit etiam
 Augustinum dicentem. Vallem suslinere penam herodis car-
 phe etc. ut supra habuisti. Sed miser quid dicam. Ecce tot se-
 moniaci inter presbiteros, seculares, et canonicos. Tot pro-
 prietarii inter claustrales. Tot concubinarij inter pastores quo-
 rum non est numerus. De alijs taceo peccatis multiplicibus
 quibus sacerdos clericorum obscuratur. Notandum est igitur
 ad sacerdotium conuolare, nisi quis velit caste et sancte
 viuere quod fecerunt antiqui sancti patres qui fuerunt ad sa-
 cerdotium valde difficiles. Legimus enim in vita patrum
 plusquam ducentos monachos fuisse in vno claustris, et vix erant
 aut quattuor, et ipse fuisse presbiteros. Et sanctus Mare-
 euangelista sibi pollicem amputasse legitur ut ineptus esset
 sacerdotio, tantum enim verebatur corporis domini consecratio-
 nem, nusquam legitur de eo quod fuerit sacerdos, similiter de sancto
 Francisco. Quis scit si predictis patribus sanctis timores
 incusserit beatus Johannes baptista qui inuitatus a domi-
 no ut eum baptizaret. Ipse autem timebat solui tangere ver-
 ticem eius. Quanto nos timere debemus cum verum corpus
 eius totaliter tractamus et manducamus? Quis enim nostrum
 fratres carissimos non ingemiscat et dicat intra se. O clemen-
 tissime deus et verissime animarum nostrarum amator. Je-
 su christe, quid aut quomodo nisi cogitasti, quod tanta magna et
 mirabilia opera nobiscum facere voluisti, et corpus totum
 sicut restes ad dexteram patris in cubum daries nostrarum

*aug⁹ de indignis ser-
uibus qui ad
alium amedi*

*Gery⁹
de missa bonam q
mali sacerdotis
an vbi*

*Sacerdos non fore
dum est inuitus*

*in vita patrum
ducentos monachos
aut quattuor fuisse
presbiteros*

*de s. marino
pollicem se amputauit*

*de s. fransisco
de s. iohanne bap^{ta}*

*S. fransisco s. marino / iohanne baptista
notis esse famulos s. fransisco*

VIII.
Two
Incunabula
bound
together
Signed by
the
Rubricator.

444Ja. Guillelmus Parisiensis; (1297?-1312?)

444Jb. Johannes; de Turrecremata, (1388-1468)

444Ja Guillelmus Parisiensis.

VITAM BONAM ET EXITVM Beatum ꝛ Ego Frater Guilhermus sacre Theologie Profes ꝛ sor minimus parisius educat[um]. Sacroru[m] euangelioꝝ ac epistolariu[m] de te[m]pore dieb[us] dominicus et sa[n] ꝛ ctis. Etiam super cōmune Apostolo[rum] Martirum. confessorum. ꝛ virginum. Et pro defunctis Expositiones in vnu[m] colligere vꝛ olume mius expertis clericis.

f 1r8v: Incipit "Postilla sup[er] euangelia• et primo domicalia (sed/icit) sensum litteralem Iuxta concord antai's euangelstarum "

Vienne (France) Eberhard Frommolt (not before 1480)

Chancery folio : 26.8 x 18 cm. Signatures: [a-x⁸ y-z⁶]. 178 of 180 (wanting blanks leaves)
Both titles bound together in later full calf over wooden boards. Many initials supplied in red and capitals stroked in a very singular way.

An extremely rare edition, printed at the second press at Vienne. Thirteen Books are assigned to Eberhard Frommolt.

"The Postilla of Guillelmus Parisiensis," Gutenberg-Jahrbuch 1959, p. 73). More than one hundred editions of the Postilla super epistolas et evangelia by Guillelmus Parisiensis were printed during the fifteenth century. The Postilla provide commentary on the Gospels to be read each Sunday and festival. The text is surviving in numerous early manuscripts, yet its authorship remains uncertain, but current consensus recognizes much of the base as Johann Herolt's work, edited and augmented by Guillelmus, a Dominican friar of Paris.

"More than one hundred editions of the Postilla super epistolas et evangelia by Guillelmus Parisiensis were printed during the fifteenth century. Surely this esteemed compilation must be regarded as one of the earliest 'best sellers', for how else can one explain why the text was not only frequently reprinted but was reissued time and time again by the same printer...Only a few facts seem to be known about Frater Guillelmus. The introduction to the Postilla, his only published work, tells us that he was a Dominican and a professor of sacred theology at Paris. This compilation of the Postilla was written down in 1437 expressly for members of the clergy and for those desirous of understanding the excerpts from the Epistles and the Evangelists, more commonly called lessons, which are read at appropriate services throughout the church year. It obviously filled a most pressing need" (Goff, "G-JB 1959, p. 73).

Worldwide holdings: of the Guillelmus Parisiensis;

France: Beaune BM, Besançon BM, Colmar BM United States Brown Univ. :Number of holding institutions 4
<https://data.cerl.org/istc/ig00654800>

France: Beaune BM, Besançon BM, Colmar BM United States Brown Univ. :Number of holding institutions 4

<https://data.cerl.org/istc/ig00654800>

GW 11926; Copinger 2861. GW 11926. ISTC ig00654800. Pellechet 5641.

Castan(Besançon): Castan, Auguste. Catalogue des incunables de la Bibliothèque Publique de Besançon. 1893. #530 .

§

444Jb. Johannes; de Turrecremata, (1388-1468)
 and Nicolas De Byard

Quaestiones Evangeliorum de tempore et de sanctis. - Nicolas De Byard (fl. c.1300). [Dictionarius pauperum:] Flos theologiae sive Summa de abstinentia. † 2 parts in 1 volume. **Quaestiones Evangeliorum de tempore et de sanctis**

[Basel: Johann Amerbach, [A copy at Frankfurt am Main has rubricator's date of 28 Sept. 1481] Price: \$35,000

Turrecremata, cardinal, was born at Valladolid in 1388, and at an early age joined the Dominican order, early distinguishing himself for learning and devotion. In 1415 he accompanied the general of his order to the council of Constance, whence he proceeded to Paris for study, and took his doctor's degree in 1423. After teaching for some time in Paris, he became prior of the Dominican house first in Valladolid and then in Toledo. In 1431 Pope Eugenius IV. called him to Rome and made him "magister sancti palatii." At the council of Basel he was one of the ablest and most prominent supporters of the view of the Roman curia, and he was rewarded with a cardinal's hat in 1439. He died in 1468. (EB)

Nicolaus of Byards [Dictionarius pauperum:] Flos theologiae sive Summa de abstinentia. is an encyclopedia of Christian philosophy, for the use of preachers, arranged alphabetically from "De abstinentia" to "De vita eterna." From the 1480s on, this was a popular collection, yet the attribution to de Byard is tentative. In this book we find the admonition that just as robbers easily have the treasure after they have broken the chest, so the devil has the soul after he has confused a man and stolen his patience, because "the heart of a fool is like a broken vessel, no wisdom at all shall it hold." It has only recently been attributed to the late fifteenth-century German Augustinian Nicolaus de Byard (cf. Bloomfield, et al., Incipits of Latin works on the virtues and vices, no. 1841).

<https://data.cerl.org/istc/it00553000>

ISTC it00553000; Goff T553; BMC III 747; GW M48236; HC 15714*; Pell Ms 11270; Polain(B) 3869; IDL 4519; IBE 5680; IGI 9889; Sheppard 2414; Pr 7566; BSB T-568.

617-678-4517

IX. Horace

Opera. Comm: Antonius Mancinellus: Add: Pseudo= Acron: Pomponius Porphyrio: Christophorus Landinus. Ed: Antonius Mancinellus

Venice: Doninus Pincius, 1495 [i.e. 1505], 5 Febr. Price: \$7,500.

Folio : ¶x∞ cm. signatures headline, roman letter, title with large woodcut vignette and 27 woodcut illustrations in the text. Beautiful woodcut initials.

The printer is often misrecorded as Philippus Pincius. Doninus Pincius worked ca. 1502-1506. The uncertainty of the date of printing stems from the misprinted colophon 'Anno a natiuate Domini.M.CCCCV.' Of the 26 woodcuts used probably 7 were expressly cut for this work, the others having been originally used for the 1490 Bible, the 1493 Livy and, according to Sander, the remainder for a 1505 Virgil 'qui nous est restée inconnue'. It is this last fact that causes him to date the book 1505. Scarce. (BMC V 496). Bound in quarter calf over wooden boards.

The unique charm of Horace's lyric poetry arises from his combination of the metre and style of the distant past—the world of the Archaic Greek lyric poets—with descriptions of his personal experience and the important moments of Roman life. He creates an intermediate space between the real world and the world of his imagination, populated with fauns, nymphs, and other divinities. He denounces corrupt morals, praises the integrity of the people of Italy, and shows a ruler who carries on his shoulders the burden of power. Other Augustan themes that appear in Horace's lyric verse include the idea of the universal character and eternity of Roman political dominion and the affirmation of the continuity of the republican tradition with the Augustan principate. At some stage Augustus offered Horace the post of his private secretary, but the poet declined on the plea of ill health. Notwithstanding, Augustus did not resent his refusal, and indeed their relationship became closer.

Ref. Goff H457; Hain 8892; Graesse III, 348; Sander 3457; GW XI Sp.754a.

United States of America copies :

- 1) Princeton Univ .2) Univ. of California,

X. 957G Richard Mediavilla [Middleton], d. 1302/3

Commentum super quartem Sententiarium.

Venice: Christophorus Arnoldus, [circa 1476-7] Price: \$22,000

Folio 31 x 21cm. a-z¹⁰ c¹⁰ e¹⁰ f¹⁰ A¹⁰ B-D⁸ (D⁸v blank and aa¹r blank) aa⁸ bb¹⁰ cc⁸ (320 leaves of 320) . This copy is Rubricated throughout with nicely complicated red initials, It is bound in an age appropriate binding of full calf over wooden boards with clasps and catches with quite impressive end bands.

Middleton, a Franciscan, theologian, and philosopher, he was born in either England or France. He studied at Paris, where he was part of the neo-Augustinian movement, defending Augustine against the inroads of Aristotelianism. Middleton's Commentary on Peter Lombard's 'Sentences' was completed in 1284. His commentary is a sober assessment of many of the positions of Thomas Aquinas. However, the tone of his eighty Quodlibet Questions, is much more critical on many issues and shows a strong anti-Thomist reaction. ¶ Furthermore; nine questions (23 to 31) in this volume form a veritable treatise on demonology, a rare type in the thirteenth century. Mediavilla's remark is singular: he is the only thinker who gives autonomy of existence to the demon, in the framework of a rational description. Mediavilla focuses on the presents of the devil and its modes of action on men. He is **THE** great thinker of the demonic turn of the 1290s.

This text offers one of the origins of a Western genre, the “novel of Satan”

¶ The questions of volume IV

23. *Did the first sin of the angel come from a good principle?*
24. *Can the angel at the moment of his creation sin?*
25. *In the first sin of the angel, was the comparison of the creature anterior, according to the order of nature, to the distancing from God?*
26. *Was the first sin of the angel pride?*
27. *Did the evil angel repent of his pride?*
28. *In the evil angels, does sin follow another sin without end?*
29. *Does the sorrow of the evil angels leave her with a certain joy?*
30. *Would the evil angels not be?*
31. *Can bad angels play our sensations?*

Nouua signa et inuenta mirabilia. glorifica manu et brachium dextrum. excita furores. et effunde iram. Hec verba scripta sunt ecclesi. 36. que sic possunt exponi ut in eis per modum orationis predicta fuerit nouorum sacramentorum institutio. mortuorum resurrectio. electorum glorificatio. et reproborum damnatio. Per signa. n. potest intelligi facta. ut eni dicit magister huius quarti di. i. c. 1. Sacramentum est sacre rei signum. Et Aug. 10. de ci. c. 5. Et dicitur de ose. di. 2. Sacrificium. sacrum est sacrum signum. Per inuouare significatur aliquid nouum institui. accipiendo inuouationem per institutionem nouorum. Per immutata mirabilia significatur ultra mirabilia que facta sunt vel fieri faciunt mirabiliora. Per manu intelliguntur operatioes. Et quia operatioes indifferentes sunt ad bonas et malas. et sole bone operatioes glorificande sunt. i. operatioes earum propter eas glorificandi sunt. id postquam dixit. Glorifica manum subiungit et brachium dextrum. ita ut legatur et. p. id est. Per operatioem. n. dextram intelligitur operatio bona. sicut et p. sinistram mala ut sit sensus. Glorifica manum et brachium dextrum. i. glorifica facientes opera bona. Excita furores. i. resuscita reprobos et dicitur furor per quedam figuratiuum modum loquendi. vnde et ad Iherosolymam insensati dicitur. vñ ut hñ sap. 5. ipsi dicit in iudicio de iustis. Nos insensati uitam illoz existimabamus insaniam. Et effunde iram. i. effunde super eos damnationem eternam. et secundum hanc expositionem in verbis oppositis raguntur quatuor. Primo factorum none. i. institutio et ueterum euacuatio. cui dicitur in noua signa. Secundo. generatio omnium resurrectio. cui dicitur. Et immutata mirabilia. Mirabilis. n. opus facit deus in mortuorum omnium resurrectioe que mo-

do sunt hominum generatio. Tertio. spalis electorum resurrectio et glorificatio simul cui dicitur. Glorifica manum et brachium dextrum. Quarto. reprobos resurrectos et damnationis eorum completo. cui dicitur. Excita furorem et effunde iram. id quibus determinat magister in hoc. 2. Per inuouationem ergo signorum ut dictum est intelligitur institutio nouorum factorum. i. factorum non. l. que sunt signa virtute medicinalia. de quo potest exponi illud quod dicitur daniel. 6. de deo. Ipe est liberator atque saluator faciens signa. i. liberationis et saluationis. quod autem liberat infirmum et sanat virtute medicinali. De eodem etiam potest exponi illud quod dicitur ad Hebreos. 2. de non. l. in nos confirmata est ceteritate deo signis et paucis interpositis seculis. spalis distributionibus. id est signis per que misteria aliter distribuitur gratia spalis scilicet sunt etiam signa singularitate mirabilia. de quo potest exponi quod dicitur. Exo. 34. Signa facias que nunc sunt uisa super terram nec ullis gentibus. In gente. n. iudeorum non erant talia signa uisa. quia facta ue. l. gratiam significabant sed non sicut ista conferrebat. Et quia signa medicinalia et mirabilia debent suscipi cum reuerentia. id est suscipiantur cum maiori reuerentia sunt predicabilia. de quibus potest exponi illud quod dicitur. Daniel. 3. Placuit mihi predicare eius signa. quia magna sunt. Predicta autem signa Christus instituit ad euacuanda factorum ue. l. imperfectionem et propter promissorum adimplentionem. et legis faciliore obseruationem que gratiam conferunt per quam legis mandata facilius adimplentur. Per immutatioes etiam mirabilium intelligitur factio mirabilium que facit deus in omnium mortuorum resuscitatione. quod est mirabilis que fuerit eorum generatio ad quam ordiatur matrimonii sacramentum. de qua resuscitatione potest exponi illud quod dicitur iob. 37. Tonabit deus in uoce sua mirabiliter et facit magna et inscrutabilia. i. que conuenienter datur intelligi mortuorum futura resurrectio. Quia sicut dicit Apocal. i. Loquere. Lanet tuba et mortui resurgent incorrupti. et in electorum precepta glorificatio. quod erit mirabilis que sit uel fuerit eorum per facta glorificatio. de qua glorificatione potest exponi illud quod dicitur in psal. 15. Dirifica misericordias tuas

¶ Middleton's link to the neo-Augustinian movement is seen especially in his treatment of the will, even though he does not entirely follow his teachers, Ware and Acquasparta. For Middleton the will is much more noble than the intellect, since it is much more noble to love God than to understand him. Understanding without the corresponding love separates man from God. However, the key to the will's nobility is its freedom. The intellect is forced by evidence when evidence is given; the will also is forced by its nature to seek the good, but it is free in choosing the means to its predetermined goal. Even if the intellect were prudent enough to show man the best means to his goal, he would not be forced to adopt them. 'For although the intellect, like a servant with a lamp, points out the way, the will, like the master, makes the decisions and can go in any direction it pleases' (Stegmüller, 722).

¶ The superiority of the human will over the intellect further manifests itself in Middleton's conception of the nature of theology. Certainly, the study of the scriptures attempts to clarify human knowledge of both creator and creatures; principally, however, it aims to stimulate man's affections. Middleton believes that scripture prescribes laws, forbids, threatens, attracts man through promises, and shows him models of behaviour that he should follow or avoid. The study of scripture perfects the soul, moving it toward the good through fear and love. It is more of a practical science than a speculative endeavour. A theology that is speculative is one that models itself on the theology of the metaphysician or philosopher and tends to reduce Christian faith to reason.

¶ The influence of Aquinas is more in evidence in Middleton's theory of knowledge. Middleton rejects the illumination theory of Bonaventure and his more loyal followers. Man's intellectual knowledge can be explained, he argues, by the abstraction performed by the agent intellect from the singulars experienced by the human senses. In short, human individuals know, and they know by means of their own intellectual efforts, not by some special divine illumination. Unlike those who endorse the illumination theory, Middleton contends that there is no direct knowledge of spiritual beings, including God. God is not the first thing known. He can be known only by starting with creatures and by reasoning about their origins or final end. Middleton died in Rheims on 30 March 1302 or 1303." [Oxford DNB]

See also Satan the Heretic: The Birth of Demonology in the Medieval West November 15, 2006 by Alain Boureau (Author), Teresa Lavender Fagan (Translator)

Goff M-424; BMC V 206. (The ISTC shows two US copies...St Louis Univ., Pius XII Memorial Library (-) & YUL – i.e. both defective) add UCLA. Goff M-424; BMC V 206. (The ISTC shows two US copies...St Louis Univ., Pius XII Memorial Library (-) & YUL – i.e. both defective) add UCLA.

nō tenet celare. nec tenet dīe. sed v̄ hoc ir-
reprehensibilis p̄t facere quod illorū dīorū
sibi melius placuerit.

¶ De quartam. q̄nōm
q̄d q̄ h̄
gilla cōfōis. ⁊ sigillū secreti accipiendo q̄ h̄
gilla secreti in gilla se h̄it sicut sapiens ⁊ i
ferius. Sigillū. n. cōfōis ē sigillū secreti. sed
non oī sigillū secreti ē sigillū cōfōis. cū. n.
unas ab alio petat cōfōis. ⁊ ille bona fide
sibi cōsulat recōmēdās sibi ut hoc cele. nel
p̄sōay que hoc cōsulat nō noiet. ille qui cō
siliū petuit oblat ad celandū p̄ sigillū se
creti. q̄d tū nō est sigillū cōfōis. ⁊ quū frā
gēs quodis sigillorū illorū mortaliter pec
cat. ⁊ crimē p̄ditionis incurrat. tū mīto gra
uius peccat frāgēs sigillū cōfōis q̄ sigillū
secreti frāgēs. quod ē dīctū q̄ sigillū cōfō
is. nec ē ex h̄mūdū q̄ h̄o fūelā illud q̄d
deū ē sibi soli s̄q̄ frāgēs sigillū secreti. n̄
si ille q̄ hoc sibi dīxerit adijerit. Ego tra
do tibi hoc sub secreto. ⁊ alius sic recipit.
q̄ si homo ab alio cōsiliū petat ⁊ ille bona
fide sibi cōsulat in secreto quās cōsuletis n̄
adīnat dīe illi q̄ sibi nō cōsuletet n̄s̄. nisi
us recipiat in secreto. tū ille cui cōsiliū da
tus ē si uideat materias talē q̄ ex reuelatōe
p̄sonē cōsuletis. p̄sona cōsuletis notabile
de trimētis incurret ⁊ reuelat. crimē p̄dō
nis incurrit. ⁊ secreti sigillū frāgit. q̄ mate
ria ⁊ natura negocij requirit q̄ ille cui fide
le cōsiliū datur ē p̄sona cōsuletis in casu p̄dō
sub secreto tenere de. minus tū potuerit ce
teris p̄s̄ q̄ si n̄dūel exp̄te sibi sub secreto
tradidit. ⁊ ille ad tādū q̄ sub secreto se
exp̄te obligat. ille ē a quo p̄tū ē cōfō
lū hoc quod sibi p̄posuit cōsiliū potens
sub secreto tenere debet.

¶ Circa litteram. Ad
dic
dīctā. supple q̄rū ad malis. ⁊ remō
rāzōis supple q̄rū ad bonos. ⁊ id aguo.
q̄ fōsūū n̄q̄ ē. nō ponit lib̄ fōsūū. ut sit
nota dubitatio de cōfōis purgatorij. s̄
tū de illo igne intelligit illud uerū d̄p̄i
p̄. Cop. q̄. quod dicit de illis q̄ edificat
ignū. fēni ⁊ stipulā. n̄t aliaque sunt frequē
ter iterata. hoc nō dī. q̄ uenialia frequē
ter iterata cōfōis in sp̄ali se necessariū. s̄ q̄ ē
magis seculy oībus dieb̄ uite sue ignomi

uolios peregrinādo p̄gat. q̄m̄ hoc p̄tia p̄
nclatoulus cōfōis. am̄quū. cū depōne l̄
iūgere. nō tamē loca p̄grinatōis illi
us i arcū monasterij ad agendū p̄tia v̄
tradit. et de pe. ⁊ re. Dīs utraque serus.

¶ Di. xxiii.
¶ Quidam. Quidam
mānū. ⁊
Sup̄is de
terminat magi de p̄tia scō
dū ēē lūi ⁊ p̄tē mīstrorū
p̄niam iūgrū. ⁊ de mō re
missionis mortaliū. ⁊ de mō remissiois ue
malū d̄c. d̄minat de re. lū dīmissiois
Et dīndū in p̄to. q̄ inq̄rī utp̄ re
deat p̄cā q̄ p̄ p̄tia dīmissā q̄. quid sit
sac̄s. ⁊ quid res ⁊ p̄tia dī. d̄olī p̄cā p̄
in. ⁊ p̄ p̄p̄at q̄nē. p̄. d̄ōt mī. uerā
opione dī. Cūno q̄m̄ p̄. opione uerū
re dī. D̄. q̄ abfōm. p̄. p̄cipal dīndū ē i
fōis sac̄s. p̄. opione dīndū q̄ p̄tia iteri
ōi ⁊ exōis s̄ tū sac̄s dī. Quidā s̄ dīe

¶ Circa banc. di. quere
dū est p̄ci
palat de. ⁊ p̄ de reditū p̄cōy dīmissō
rū. q̄ de p̄tia ut ē sac̄s. p̄. Circa p̄. que
rū. s̄ q̄ uerū p̄cā dīmissā possit redi
re eadē in numero quātū ad culpā. p̄. n̄
oīa p̄cā dīmissā p̄ legīs mortale p̄cōy re
deat eadē s̄p̄e l̄ p̄tia q̄rū ad culpā. p̄. n̄
q̄m̄ ad p̄nā. p̄. uerū iūgratūdo sit sp̄a
le p̄cōy. p̄. uerū maios sit iūgratūdo in
casu ab innocētia q̄ i casu a uerā p̄tia.

¶ Primo ostendo
q̄ p̄cā dīmissā possit redire eadē in nume
ro quātū ad culpā. Aug. p̄. l̄. de bap. cō.
tra d̄sanctū ultra me. Red̄ dīmissā pec
cata uerū s̄na charitas nō ē spiritūme d̄is
docet de illo sermo que cū inuenerit deb̄
notē d̄cē mīnū salūtoy d̄p̄cēt oīa dīmis
sit. Ille autē cōfōis sūi q̄ ei debet cētū
denarios cū m̄ p̄na nō fuit. nullū eū dīo
reddere que ei dīmiserat. s̄re magi in l̄
h̄ dī. p̄. ⁊ de pe. dī. q̄. p̄. 4. s̄. s̄. f̄. s̄. f̄. s̄. f̄.
randū. s̄. nō ex corde dīmittit q̄ i non
deliquit. illud rurū exp̄t quod tū nobis
p̄ p̄tia dīmissā et ḡuū d̄m̄. s̄re p̄ ḡra
lequēte b̄a m̄na q̄ p̄cā mortale fuit.

XI. 277] Orosius, Paulus Orosius (385-420).

Historiae adversus paganos/ edited by Aeneas Vulpes. Scias velim humanissime lector:
Aeneam Vulpem Vicentinum priorem sanctae crucis adiutorem Laurentio Brixiensi Historias
Pauli Orosii quae continentur hoc codice:

[Vicenza]: Hermannus Liechtenstein, [c.1475].

price \$ 21,000

Folio 28.5 x 20cm. [1-7]⁸ [8]⁶ [9-12]⁸ [13]⁶. 100 leaves unnumbered. In this copy there is a large opening initial in green, red, blue, and yellow, with floral extensions in the margin, other initials in red and blue. Initial spaces, most with guide letters, rubricated. It is bound in full modern vellum of appropriate style. "As this book is the only one of Liechtenstein's editions which has no printed signatures it is presumably his earliest work" —BMC Hermanus is the second printer in Vincenza.

The Second edition of Orosius's universal history, written to counter the prevailing belief among non-Christians that disasters which had befallen civilisation were the result of the pagan gods, angry with worshippers turning to Christianity. This history is a continuation of the thrust of Augustine's "City of God. Augustine urged Orosius to write this history to refute Symmachus who in an address to Emperor

Valentinianus in 384 C.E. alleged that the Roman Empire was crumbling due to Christianity. Orosius was a Gallaecian Chalcedonian priest, historian and theologian, a student of Augustine of Hippo as well as Saint Jerome. This history begins with the creation and continues to his own day, was an immensely popular and standard work of reference on antiquity throughout the Middle Ages and beyond. Its importance lay in the fact that Orosius was the first Christian author to write not a church history, but rather a history of the secular world interpreted from a Christian perspective. The work treats world history as a concrete proof of the apocalyptic visions of the Bible. This became a kind of textbook of universal history for the Middle Ages; and there are many manuscripts exist all over Europe. Orosius's work is crucial for the understanding of early

Christian approaches to history, the development of universal history, and the intellectual life of the Middle Ages, for which it was both an important reference work but also a defining model for the writing of history.

Goff O-97; H *12099; GW M28420; BMC VII 1035; Bod-inc O-027; BSB-Ink O-82; ISTC io00097000; Goff O-97

A dedication proceeds the incipit:

Scias velim humanissime
 Lector: Aeneam Vulpem
 Vicentinum Priorem San
 ctae Crucis adiutore
 Laurentio Brixienſi his
 torias Pauli Orosii quae
 continentur hoc codice
 quam accuratissime po
 tuit castigatte. Cui non
 improbando sane labori
 si quid ex ingenio tuo
 vel melius vel aptius ad
 dendum putabis: id hono
 re eius integro facias
 obsecro: quod est non
 ingrati animi officium.

On the final leaf there is a colophon in verse by Æneas Vulpes, who was one of the correctors for Hermann of Lichtenstein's Press.

Bartholomeus paiellus/eques Vicentinus in P. Orosium.

Vt ipse titulus margine in primo docet:

Orosio nomen mihi est.

Librariorum quicquid erroris fuit:

Exemit Aeneas mihi.

Meq̄ imprimendum tradidit non alteri

Hermanne: q̄ soli tibi.

Hermanne nomen huius artis & decus:

Tuæq̄ laus Colonia.

Quodsi situm orbis: sique nostra ad tempora

Ab orbis ipsa origine

Quisq̄ tumultus bellaq̄ & cædes uelit

Cladesq̄ nosse: me legat.

Bartholomeus paiellus/eques Vicentinus in P. Orosium

Vt ipse titulus margine in primo docet:

Orosio nomen mihi est.

Librarior[um] quicquid erroris suit:

Exemit Aeneas mihi.

Meq[ue] imprimendum traditit non alteri

Hermanne:q[ue] soli tibi.

Hernanne nomen huius artis & decus:

Tuæq[ue] laus Colonia.

Quodsi situm orbis :sique nostra ad tempora.

Ab orbis ipsa origine bellaq[ue] & cædes uelit

Quisq[ue] tumultus: bella[que] & cædes uelit.

Cladesq[ue] nosse: me legat.

Liber iste e[st] d[omi]ni Johannis Maler

Durum patientia vincit

Johan Bartscheider

Ex Valle Venusta 1608

Ad usum Frum Ord. Erem. S. Aug. Rattenberg

16. 1. . . .

Ad Conuentum F. F. Eremit. S. P. Augustini in Rattenberg

On back: *In usu societatis Jesu Venepotij 1663*

On Next leaf: *Rattenberg*

Est autem huius operis ordo talis. Primo ponuntur sermones d[omi]nicales de tempore per anni circulu[m]. Secundo de sanctis/ Tercio q[ua]dragesimale Iacobi de Foragine/ Q[ua]rto concordantia quatuor euangelista[rum] in passiiones d[omi]nicam a magistro Nicolao Dinkelspubell collectam."/ end of leaf m8: "Sermones Peregrini de tempore finiunt.

[Ulm: Johann Zainer, not after 1479]

Price: \$11,000.

(A copy now in Munich BSB has an ownership inscription dated 1479)

Folio 27 x 20 cm.

"Pars I (188): a-d⁸, e-k^{8/6}, l-m⁸, A-C⁸, D-I^{8/6}, K-N⁸; (N⁸ blank and removed) "Pars II

(50.): a-f^{8/6}, g⁸; 3. "Pars III (40.): A-E⁸/ [276 (instead of 278) The two blank leaves (162 & 188) are missing. Rubricated throughout. Bound in contemporary calf over wooden boards, with catches and clasp restored. Rebacked with the spine restored using old material, cover covers rubbed and with small missing parts). I have located only two U.S. copies both defective. This Copy has very interesting Provenance.

¶ Peregrinus of Opole, was a Silesian Dominican friar, Prior in Wroclaw and Racibórz and Provincial of the Polish-East German Order Province. He was twice elected a provincial of his Order and became designated an inquisitor of Wroclaw by the pope John XXII. His major literary achievement is this twofold collection of Latin sermons: Sermones de tempore (sermons on the feasts of the liturgical year) and Sermones de sanctis (sermons on feasts of particular saints).

Jacobus de Voragine wrote several series of sermons, the Lenten sermons (Quadragesimale) were written between 1277 and 1286. These sermons were only slightly less popular than his "Legend," and also known as 'Golden' on account of their popularity (there are more than 300 known manuscript copies).

The genre of the Sermones quadragesimale did not exist as a distinct genre before the 1260's This Dominican best-seller author Jacopo da Voragine, and the works of preachers from his

own generation, like Peregrinus von Opeln [See above] have a strong sermo modernus structure and contain numerous exempla drawn from the world of nature.

¶Nicolaus de Dinkelsbuel. Magister in 1390, BUT The ascription of the Concordantia to Nicolaus de Dinkelsbühl (c 1360-1433) is mistaken. Although he is known as the author of a passion story (Collecta et praedicata de passione Christi. 1472). He did not produce a concordance to it, but he is in fact listed as one of the authors cited in the work. (See A Madre, Nicolaus de Dinkelsbühl, Leben

und Schriften, 1965, p 310.)

Only two North American copies, both defective.

- 1) Harvard University (- ff 189-278)
- 2) Bryn Mawr College, (ff 239-278)

Goff P267; ISTC ip00267000.

Fascicule XXX.

The fifteenth century

HC 12581*; C 4407; IGI 7404; IBP 4241; Madsen 3083; Voull(B) 2629,5; Hubay(Augsburg) 1582; Hubay(Eichstätt) 794; Borm 2059; Walsh 909; Rhodes(Oxford Colleges) 1340; BMC II 529; BSB-Ink P-183; GW M30917 - Wegener, Zainer 9 - BSB-Ink P-183 - Proctor 2542.

XIII. 145J Paulus Pergulensis**Logica magistri Pauli Pergulensis.**

Venice : Johannes Emericus, de Spira, 22 Feb. 1495/96, Price: \$11,000

Quarto 21 x 15 cm. a-e⁸, f⁴ 44 of 44 leaves (complete), Bound in an incunable leaf over boards. The Signature of Thomas Stewart, Knight of St. John of Jerusalem, dated Rome 1837 on the title Light dampstaining in lower margins throughout, title and last page soiled. Italy, the centre of humanism, produced the best logicians of the Renaissance. Paulus Pergulensis (d. 1451) was a pupil of Paul of Venice, author of the *Logica magna* and *parva*. Introducing the theory of reference, sometimes called supposition, is an explanation of the ways in which words refer to objects in function of certain linguistic signs.

Paul of Venice maintains a threefold division: Material Reference, Simple Reference, and Personal Reference, all of which are identified The present is a more succinct and highly systematized logic, composed entirely in the form of theses. From 1420 to 1454 Pergulensis taught logic and natural philosophy, and then also mathematics, astronomy and theology, to the Venetian school of Rialto (founded in 1408), to which he gave a real university organization. He was nominated (1448) bishop of Koper, which he renounced so as not to leave the teaching. We are left of him, manuscripts or press, some treatises of logic (*Dubia in consequentias Strodi*, *De sensu composite and divided*, *In regulas insolubilium* , *De scire et dubitare* , *Compendium logicae*), in which he discusses the new logical doctrines of the Oxford school in Padua by Paolo Veneto. Paul of Pergula (died 1451) became the first publicly paid lecturer in philosophy in Venice, where he was officially honored in a public ceremony. In 1448, he was offered a bishopric, which he refused, and at the end of his life he accepted the administration of the Church of Saint John Almoner. He translated some works of Aristotle from Greek to Latin and was considered "on a par with the renowned Greek and Latin philosophers" (Brown, pp. vi-vii). Depending on the *Logica Parva* of Paul of Venice, *De sensu composito et diviso* should be regarded as a "mosaic of the treasury of logic known at the time" (Brown, p. viii). Lohr, C.H. "A Note on Manuscripts of Paulus Venetus, *Logica*," *Manuscripta*, 17(1973), pp. 35-36; reprinted in *Bulletin de philosophie medievale*, 15 (1973), pp. 145-146.

All editions are rare:

P190 1481 Ratdolt 2 us Pml ,HeHl

617•678•4517

- P191. 1483 Tortis 2 us Hehl, JHU
 P192. 1486 Tortis 2 us UPaL, (EHLS Rockport maine)
 P193. 1489 Tridinesis 1 us LOC
 P194. 1491 deStrada 1 us WartG
 P195 1495 Emericus , 3 us NewL, PrinUL, and this copy
 P196. 1489 Quarengiia 3 us LC, UILL, YUL.

Paulus Pergulensis ca -1451. Ennio De Bellis, Nicoletto Vernia e Agostino Nifo: aspetti storiografici e metodologici, Congedo, 2003, p. 9.

Logica; and, Tractatus de sensu composito et diviso by Paolo della Pergola, edited by Mary Anthony Brown, Saint Bonaventure, New York: Franciscan Institute, 1961.

<http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/paul-venice/>

BABCOCK, ROBERT G. "AN UNRECORDED SESSA IMPRINT." The Yale University Library Gazette, vol. 64, no. 3/4, 1990, pp. 124–131. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/40859597.
 Goff P195; H 12626; R 1314; Sander 5476; IBE 4363; IGI 7322; IBPort 1357; Horch(Rio) Suppl 13; Mendes 957; BSB-Ink P-91.050; GW M30234

Two US copies see above.# P195

XIV. 305J Pelbartus de Themeswar

Sermones Pomerii fratris Pelbarti de Themeswar diui ordinis sancti francisci de Sanctis: Incipiunt feliciter

Hagenau: Heinrich Gran, for Johannes Rynman, 30 September, 1501. [imp[re]ssi ... p[er] industriu[m] Henricu[m] Gran Price: \$16,000

Folio 27 x 19 cm. π^6 [x]⁶ a-b⁸ c⁶ d-e⁸ f⁶ g-h⁸ i⁶ k-l⁸ m⁶ n-o⁸ p⁶ q-s⁸ t⁶ v-x⁸ y⁶ z⁸ A⁸ B⁶ C-D⁸ E⁶ F-G⁸H⁶ I-K⁸ L⁶ M-N⁸ O⁶ P-Q⁸ R⁶ S-T⁸ U⁶ X-Y⁸ Z⁶ e⁸ • [leaves 12 and 358 blank]. This copy is bound contemporary blind-stamped leather over wooden boards from an Augsburg workshop operating between 1482 and 1500.

¶ There is Early monastic ink title to fore-edge and ink inscription to front free endpaper, nineteenth century ink inscription to front pastedown, wormholes to opening and closing leaves, a couple of unobtrusive wormholes extending into first few quires touching a few letters, corners of two leaves torn well clear of text, leaf A8 soiled at edges and possibly supplied from another copy, occasional very light paper browning otherwise internally clean. Binding worn with

minor chips and losses, spine with minor loss especially at head, paper monastic library label to foot of spine, upper edge of rear board damaged exposing wood beneath (not affecting blind rolls), remains of hasps and clasps, light marks to centre of each board where central brass bosses were once affixed.

¶ The Bavarian binding and inscription to its front free endpaper indicate very early acquisition by the medieval Benedictine Monastery of the Abbey of Irsee, Bavaria. Upon the dissolution of Bavarian monasteries in 1803 the volume was acquired by Munich Court Library; a nineteenth century ink inscription to the front pastedown notes the copy to have been a duplicate and it was doubtless sold between

1815 and 1859 when the library started a series of large auctions to dispose of surplus items. Sometime after 1880 it was acquired by the Benedictine monastery of Erdington Abbey, Birmingham, England, established for monks expelled in Bismarck's kulturkampf from Beuron, Prussia. In 1922 the Erdington monastery was dissolved following return of its monks to Beuron after World War I, and its library appears to have been subsequently disbursed.

Hain 12557 (describing an imperfect copy). An attractive copy of this rare early work in entirely original state with substantial provenance. Fourth or so edition of this collection of sermons by Pelbartus de Themesvar, Hungarian Franciscan at the St. John Monastery

in Buda. The popular text was first published in 1499 He was born in 1430 in Temesvár, Hungary (now Timi oara, Romania). In 1458 he went to the University of Kraków. In 1463 he was licensed in Theology. Possibly in 1471 he left Kraków as a doctor, then in 1483 he is mentioned in the Franciscan Community Annales of St. John Monastery in Buda, the Hungarian Capital city. After 1483 his writings began to be published in print. The first printed edition of his Sermons dates from 1498. In 1503 a printed version of his lecture notes was published. Pelbartus died on 9 January 1504 in Buda, as a highly distinguished author and professor. Hungarian versions of his writings in manuscript date from 1510.

ISTC ip00252500, citing holdings at 15 locations globally with none in the US or UK; Not in Goff.; GW M30525; H 12557*; Sajó-Soltész p. 767; Günt(L) p.65; Wilhelmi 479a; VD16 P1165

[Gesamtkatalog der Wiegendrucke](https://gesamtkatalogderwiegendrucke.de/docs/M30525.htm) • <https://gesamtkatalogderwiegendrucke.de/docs/M30525.htm> • Letzte Änderung: 2012-04-17

Holdings

Austria Graz, FranziskanerZB (imperfect)
 Scheibbs, Kapuziner
 Schwaz, Franziskaner (Ink U1/1-02)
 EstoniaTallinn Arch
 GermanyBerlin, Staatsbibliothek (3)
 Gotha ForschLB
 Greifswald GeistlMin
 Leipzig Universitätsbibliothek
 Mainz GM/StB (2, Ink.1107,2553),München, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, München MetropolitanKap (I117/1a)
 München UB
 Rostock Universitätsbibliothek
 Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibliothek
 HungaryBudapest Bibl nat (,Univ (2))
 Berlin, Staatsbibliothek Preußischer Kulturbesitz
 Bibliothek der Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (Sigel: 19)
 Budapest, Országos Széchényi Könyvtár (Nationalbibliothek)
 Freiburg/Breisgau, Universitätsbibliothek
 Halle, Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Sachsen-Anhalt
 Innsbruck, Provinzbibliothek der Kapuzinerprovinz Österreich-Südtirol
 Kremsmünster, Stiftsbibliothek
 Rostock, Salzburg, Diözesanbibliothek
 Universitätsbibliothek Zentralbibliothek/Teilbibliotheken in Eichstätt (Sigel: 824)
 Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibliothek

Bermo

1

Incipit Domeriū

sermonis de sancto q̄ ad p̄t̄ p̄mā s̄s h̄emalē.
In nomine dñi Jesu. Ad castitatem manū eius
 Martine sc̄ scripta p̄m̄ nolite t̄rāctā: q̄m̄q̄
 s̄cōs: lau dem z gl̄iam. Sermones de sanctis p̄
 anni circuli incipiūt. Et q̄m̄ p̄mo de cōs An
 dra ap̄to Bermo. l. cum legenda ip̄tus.

Simili pena

seruus cū dño afflic^o est: et
 popular^{is} hō regi similia pas
 sus ē. Sap. viiij. et ad laudē
 ac gl̄iam huius festiuitatis.
 Sicut deuotissim^o Berni. air. fideles miles vul
 nera sua nō senti dñi benigni sui regi vulnera in
 tuet. Nā fil^{ius} mori est ille q̄ videt regē vulnera
 sui: sanguine cruciatu: se ab q̄ vulnerē ipse de bel
 lo subtrahat. Cū ḡ xps dñs z rex nri in bello ḡ di
 aboli videat vulnerat^{us} z cruciat^{us} p̄fusus: valde
 nob^{is} r̄cūditū: turpe z danabile est si nolim^{us} p̄o
 xpo pugne ḡ diabolica vicia. No citat^{us} conside
 rans dñs Andreas: voluit p̄ cruciatu dño iesu
 subire crucis p̄ntibulū. p̄ter qd merito hęc ḡ ba
 rtemas de nob^{is} cōmendari videt.

Dño de passūis s̄ctitudinē. Simili pena
 Sō dō de seruuis s̄ctitudie. quia cū dño af
 flicus est ip̄tē seruus.

Tertio de gl̄ie celestis magnitudinē: q̄ sequit
 er hoc q̄ ip̄tē popular^{is} hō regi ip̄to s̄ctū passus ē.
 Nā vt scribit Eccl. xiiij. ca. S̄ctia magna est sequi
 dñm. qd pōt esse aliud thēma sermōnis.

B Luca p̄mū de passionis xpi s̄ctitudinē. p̄
 documēto zdulso ponit ista vitz. q̄ dñs xpian^{us}
 exēplo bñ Andree debet p̄formit xpo pan in cru
 ce. l. Vere p̄nie si vult cū iesu crucifixo regē. Dec
 cōdūlo ondit^{us} triplicat. Primo autoritate. nā
 In Amb. xviij. dicit xps dñs. Qui vult venire post
 me abneget semetip̄m z tollat crucē suā z sequa
 tur me. vñ Beryf. Nō sufficit ad salutē crux sua
 finētia. Qui p̄nia mala cōmittit iustū est vt per
 xpianū pena diluat. Dicit. j. p̄t. ij. In b vocat
 est charissim^{us} qz z xps passus ē. p̄ nob^{is} v. reer.
 vte. vte. r̄.

Sēdo rōne. Nā vt dicit Berni. sup
 Lan. ler. vj. Xpianū nomē a xpo deriuat vt ip̄m
 imēct. Et Aug^o. de vita xpiana dicit. Nō in b nob
 omē em qz xpianū dicimur blādiamur. sed p̄t b
 etiā nos iudicādo credam^{us} si nob^{is} nomen fru
 stra videm^{us} alienū. Sed qm̄ ip̄m opozuit pa
 ti crucē z ita intrare i gl̄iam suā. ḡ multo foit^{us} xpian
 ū vt intraret in gl̄iaz nō suā sed xp̄i op̄t pan cru
 cē p̄nie. sic ait Ber. Nam vt dicit. j. q̄. ij. Sacerdos
 Et. xij. q̄. ij. Charitate. Iustū est vrilli soli p̄cāq̄
 stūpēdū. i. s̄ctitatē z gl̄ie q̄ ip̄dērit laboris ob
 sequiū. Tertio exēplo vt s̄ctitudie. Ex p̄mo exē
 plo theologico. Nā videmus aliq̄s fideles noie

em q̄ fide sola sequunt^{ur} r̄m̄ sed op̄m̄tant dñi
 aboli. de dñb T. iij. j. Lōficet^{us} seroisse de ze. fa
 cte aut negant. S; q̄ vultas i b: cū vt Jac. ij. dicit
 fides sine op̄b̄o mortua ē. J. i. d. Quid p̄dest q̄
 fidei iugimur deo z op̄b̄o disingimur. Unqz b
 vt dicit Berni. Ad amulū in ḡre dānatois est
 fidei nra si nō fm̄ ea opamur. Alios xpianōs nō
 vimus q̄ sequunt^{ur} xp̄o qz p̄formant fide z opere
 sed ad xps. qz nō p̄seuerat sed in p̄cā recidiunt
 Et qd de talib. Audiant Berni. ij. canonica. ij.
 Facta s̄rillū in ḡq̄ posteriora deteriora p̄oib^o.
 Longit^{us} em̄ eis illud p̄uerbium. Lan reuerfus
 ad vomitū z sus lota in volutabro lui. Tercelle
 Leo papa. Nō inchoāto sed p̄seuerāto dabit
 p̄m̄iū. Dicā ḡ cū Aug. oib^{us} ep̄colis. q̄ ḡ si labo
 rabit in semē nō gaudet in messe. qm̄ dicent
 ap̄to. Que semiat hō bōc z metet. l. p̄ pas ignem
 crūi z p̄ p̄nia regnū eoz. S; dō idē cōdit^{us} ex
 plo p̄s̄rilo. Nā apes p̄ suo regē mori paratē
 et si q̄ offēderit regē. ap̄to acilio tē mo: dē co
 ra regē vt ait Am̄. in bēta. q̄no mag^{is} rōnal^{is} bō
 offēdas creat^{us} ē debet p̄nia agere. Tertio exē
 plo politico. Unqz dicit regē papū qz fēf de mag^{is}
 Alexādro q̄ p̄ ip̄o militēs mori pan erāt. Nam
 ipse Alexāder cū pauc^{is} militib^{us} mltos aduclari
 oū dēuclat adeo qz Dar^{us} p̄t cū missit illi i n̄r
 cōs plures saccos plenos papauz grānis di.
 q̄ in tācō pio sa m̄tūdine veniret ḡ illū. Alexan
 der remisit sibi sacculū vnū plenū pipib^{us} di. q̄ si
 cur paucaas pipez cōdit^{us} b; sapoz mltos; pas
 pauz. sic pauc^{is} militēs Alexādrī superat mlti
 tudinē exērat^{us} Darj b̄ ideo. qz militēs Alexādrī
 pan erāt mori. p̄ suo regē dñi vidēbant acē p̄mo
 inuadēte ip̄e p̄m̄. ḡ exērat^{us} mltō mag^{is} debem^{us}
 nos p̄ xpo rē. L. Sed qm̄ aliq̄ xpian^{us} debet
 exēplo bñ Andree assimilari xpo i crucē b̄ p̄nie
 R̄ndēf q̄ sic crux bñ Andree fuit crux p̄ni p̄s̄t
 onis s̄cti papie q̄m̄q̄ sic z crux p̄nie n̄re debet
 assilari xpo vt p̄formit panamur in q̄m̄ papū
 is fm̄ nūqz. q̄m̄q̄ vultēz xp̄i p̄ gr̄atiuacōne.

- Primo in panēdo inno ceter.
- Secundo amāter.
- Tertio cōdonāter.
- Quarto p̄seuerāter.
- Quinto humilitē.

Dño inoent. Sic em̄ xps dñs inoēt passus
 est. Et p̄ s̄q̄ parz q̄ in sinistra manu vuln^{us} iusec
 pit z in p̄penū in celo referuabit^{ur} r̄f̄ructioēz
 vt significet qz nulli vnq̄ s̄mitire nō curit. em̄ vt
 agn^{us} ad occasione inoēt dūc^{us} ē. Et s̄q̄. Sic z
 Andreas passus ē inoent vt testat^{us} ois xp̄s
 di. Innoēt bñ; h̄m̄q̄m̄ sine cā damnat^{us}. In z
 xpian^{us} debet sic p̄nie crucē pan vt de cero nō nec
 cet sed viuat inno ceter. J. i. i. Innoēt est z nō p̄t
 nūtes q̄ adbucaq̄ qd p̄nūz. Nā p̄nia est p̄nūca
 mala plāgere z plāgēda si cōmittere de p̄. di. iij.
 s. j. Sēdo amāter. Unqz sic p̄ s̄q̄ xps coz vulnē
 ratū suare voluit z volūtate ē passus z dēdit^{us}
 a z

Price: \$7,500

XV. 413J Johannes Reuchlin

(1455-1522)

Vocabularius breuiloquus triplici
 alphabeto diuersis ex autorib[us]
 necno[n] corpore vtriusq[ue] iuris
 collectus ad latinu[m] sermone[m]
 capessendu[m] vtilissimus.

Basel, [Johann Amerbach], 1478.

Folio: π^6 b^3 - r^{10} S^8 s^{10} t^8 u^{10} v^{10} w^{10} x^{10} y^{12} ; 1-5 10 6-7 8 , 8 10 (last leaf blank). **Incomplete and manipulated copy, 18 leaves are missing, namely the 6 unsigned sheets. at the beginning and the leaves. a1-10 and b1-2.** The last 8 signature bound in front

This has a complete vocabulary A-Z First edition. Restored blind stamped pigskin from the early 16th century over wooden boards with roll stamping or ornamental leaves and blind stamped tooling of reformation leaders, Luther, Melanchthon etc. (spine renewed, missing clasps, rubbed and scraped, somewhat browned and stained. This book has some wonderful initials (one on the cover of this catalogue in addition to the humorous faces and complex geometric infilling. This is the first Dated book from Amerbach and the first book by Reuchlin, one of the greatest Scholars of his time. This is a very scarce title.

¶ The Vocabularius, a Latin dictionary, is the first work of Johannes Reuchlin (1455-1522). This is the first printing, this important humanist published the first time while studying in Basel. - Rubricated throughout red. -.. - In places a little more browned, slightly foxed, partly with wet margins, few finger and ink stains, isolated sheet with small tears in the margins, overall in good condition. - A double page with ms.old hand annotations. This book also contains a preface and contents on verso of first leaf. The main text is preceded by three short philological texts: Ars diphthongandi (leaves π^2 r- 3 v) by Guarinus and De arte punctandi (leaves π^3 v) and De accentu (leaves π^3 v- 6v) by Johannes de Lapide.

BM 15th cent.; III, p. 745 (IB. 37253); BN cat. des incun.; R-101; BSB-Ink.; R-143; Goff; R-155 ◊ copies: Harvard, College of Physicians of Philadelphia, Free Library of Philadelphia, Indiana State, New York Public, Huntington, U.N.C.

XVI. 438J Ripelin, Hugo 1205-1270 (formerly ascribed to Albertus Magnus)

Compendium theologicæ veritatis [with table by Thomas Dorniberg]

Ulm: Johann Zainer, ca. 1478-80). [not after 1480]

[CIBN dates this as not after 1480 from the date of rubrication in Württemberg LB copy (cf. Amelung, Frühdruck)] furthermore a copy in the Klemm collection, at Leipzig has a rubricator's date: "1481" Imprint from incipit on leaf [2r] which reads: *Theoloyce veritatis co[m]pendium alphabetico ordine registratum ac in regali opido vlma per Joa[n]nem zainer impressum feliciter incipit.*

Price: \$24,000

Folio: 26 x 19 cm. unsigned [a⁸, b⁶, c-t⁸, u⁶, x⁶]. 162 leaves. 40 lines, single column, headlines. Gothic type (type: 4:96G, 5:136G). Each Signature is guarded by vellum from a reused manuscript. Many initials rubricated in red, (excepting most of book two?) capitals accented in red, and section titles underlined in red.

This copy is bound in original red doe skin over beveled wooden boards, decoratively stamped in blind with alternating floral and fleur-de-lis pattern, remnants of original clasps, old paper label on spine, boards and spine heavily rubbed and worn, chip out of top corner of rear board, lower corner very worn, spine ends chipped.

¶ There is an old catalogue slip\description on front paste-down quoting a Katalogle description from "T. (sic. Jacques) Rosenthal " Buch-und Kunstantiquariat katalogle 18: 1898 number 244; [which dates this edition at 1468] ¶ Most likely typed by WR Siegart who received this book from Dr. Grimm. More interesting, on the front pastedown there is an ownership note by Jacob Hartlieb active 1493-1513. There is a note free endpaper which is a reference, noting a page number in a book by Jakob Wimpheling of Schlestadt, (1450-1528.) licentiate of theology, on the lives of the bishops of Strasbourg, [specifically] in the life of Henry of Germany, the one-time(?) (looks like olim) 65th (?) bishop, writes on folio 42: Then follows Wimpheling's passage. By the way, this Henry has got to be: Henri de Geroldseck active (1263-1273). Wimpheling notes that he was bishop in 1265.

¶ Wimpheling co-authored a book with Hartlieb. *De fide co[n]cubinaru[m] in sacerdotis. Questio accessoria causa ioci et vrbanitatis in q[uo]dlibeto Heydelburge[n]si determinata, quibusda[m] nouis addito[n]ibus denuo illustrata. Je[m] Questio minus principalis, de eisde[m] facetie causa, p[er] magistru[m] Jacobu[m] Hartlieb determi[n]ata . Ach lieue els. biß myr holt.*

Therefor it is not unreasonable to think that both Hartlieb and Wimpheling were friends/colleagues.

On the front past-down is later ownership evidence, an armorial book-plate of German doctor and incunabula collector Ferdinand Herscher (15??-1646) book-plate of Theological Seminary Library, Gettysburg, PA. There are two paper fragments in two

different hands laid in at front. lengthy early description in ink on recto of front blank; title in ink at head of first printed leaf; Small scattered worming; damp staining at fore-edge of first 14 leaves; minor dampstaining at bottom edge.

Johann Zainer (d. ca. 1523) was the second printer based in Ulm. Among others, he is remembered for printing the first German translation of Boccaccio's "De claris mulieribus" in 1473. Only 1.4% of ISTC recorded editions were printed in Ulm.

The "Compendium theologiae" has a long

history of being misattributed to an array of authors such as Albert Magnus, Thomas Aquinas, Thomas Dorinberg, and Bonaventure, among others, but is now more certainly considered to be by Hugo Ripelin. The Compendium most probably, if not certainly, was written by Hugh of Stasburg. Other works attributed to him are: "Commentarium in IV libros sententiarum"; "Quodlibeta, quaestiones, disputationes et variae in divinos libros explanationes"., a Dominican theologian from Strasbourg. Thomas Dorinberg, who compiled the edition of 1473 with an index, was for a long time looked upon as the author; others attributed it to Thomas Aquinas.

Among other theologians to whom it was ascribed are Hugh of Saint Cher, Alexander of Hales, Aureolus, the Oxford Dominican Thomas of Sutton, Peter of Tarantasia and others. Apart from the works of Thomas Aquinas, the "Compendium" was the most widely read work of Dominican theology, being used as a textbook for close to 400 years. The Compendium is indeed a monumental achievement. It is notable for its superb organization, its concise exposition of an amplitude of topics and of supporting rationales. It is also, for the most part, written in clear Latin, making it more easily accessible to clergy who may not have been as fluent in Latin as were the monks. The Compendium is divided into seven books, each having its own set of themes, as indicated by these books' titles:

- (1) On the Nature of the Deity;
- (2) On the Works of the Creator;
- (3) The Corrupting Effect of Sin;
- (4) On the Humanity of Christ;
- (5) Sanctifying-Effect of Graces;
- (6) The Efficacy of Sacraments;
- (7) On the Last Times and on the Punishments of Those Who are Evil and Rewards of Those Who are Good.

Each of the books is sub-divided into a series of specific issues the development of which is meant to give guidance to preachers and to students of theology. The fact that these issues are so central to Christian belief helps to explain why there survive in 59 printed editions.

ISTC ia00233000: Goff A233; H 438*; Amelung, Frühdruck I 36; Bod-inc A-105; GW 599; BSB-Ink H-399; GW 599 WEVENER #6
(Not in BMC);

¶See: Wegener :Die Zainer in Ulm: Ein Beitrag zur Geschichte des Buchdrucks im XV. Jahrhundert and Amelung, Peter. Der Frühdruck im deutschen Südwesten, 1473-1500. Bd. 1 [etc]. Stuttgart, 1979- [in progress]. I 36

<https://data.cerl.org/istc/ia00233000>

United States: 1) Union Theo. Seminary 2) Cornell Univ. 3) Duke Univ.

Bermo

1

Incipit Domeriū

Sermo de sancto q̄ ad pie d̄ma sc̄s h̄emalē.
 In nomine dñi Jesu Ad sc̄ssime mat̄ eius
 D̄ne ac sc̄raphia patr̄ nostri sc̄alāi om̄ḡs
 sc̄oz laudē et gl̄iam Sermones de sanctis p̄
 anni circuli inap̄it. Et q̄dam primo de sc̄to An
 drea ap̄to Sermo. l. cum legenda ipsius.

Simili pena

Seruus cū dño afflic̄ est: et
 popularis b̄ regi similita pas
 sus ē. Sap. xvij. et ad laudē
 et gl̄iam diuine festiuitatis.
 Sicut deuotissim⁹ Bern. ait fidelis miles vul
 nera sua nō sentit dñi benigni sui regis vulnera in
 tuē. Nā fili⁹ moir. est ille q̄ vidēs rege vulnera
 nū sanguie cruciat̄i se absq̄ vulnere ipse de b̄o
 lo subtrahat. Lij. s̄p̄s dñs ⁊ rec̄ n̄ in bello ⁊ di
 abolū videat vulnerat⁹ ⁊ cruore p̄fusus: valde
 nob̄ uectū: turpe ⁊ danabile est si nolim⁹ pro
 xpo puḡre ⁊ diabolica uia. No cū dñs confide
 rans dñs Andreas: uoluit. p̄ amēctio dño iesu
 subire crucis patibuli. p̄ter qd̄ merito bec̄ t̄ba
 themas de eo accipiunt. In quib⁹ ipse dñs An
 dreas de r̄to cōmendari uidet.

Primo de seruanis similitudine. Simili pena.
 Secūdo de seruans similitudine. quia cū dño af
 flicus est ipse seruus.
 Terno de gl̄ie celestis magnitudinis: q̄ sequit̄
 er boḡ ipse popularis b̄ regi xpo s̄lta passus ē.
 Nā ut scribit̄ Ec̄l. xviij. ca. S̄ta magna est sequi
 dñm. qd̄ p̄t esse aliud thema sermonis.

⁊ Circa p̄mū de passionis xpi similitudine. p̄
 do cūmēto dñs ponit. ista uis. q̄ ois xpian⁹
 exēplo b̄i Andree debet p̄formari xpo pati in cru
 ce. l. vere p̄nic si uult cū iesu crucifixo reḡre. Dec
 cōdūso onidit̄ triplic̄. Primo auroitate. nā
 Mat̄h. xvi. dicit̄ xps dñs. Qui uult uenire post
 me abneget semetip̄m ⁊ tollat crucē suā ⁊ sequa
 tur me. vñ L̄z̄y. Nō sufficit ad salutē crux sua
 sine tua. Qui p̄ria mala cōmittit uultū est ut per
 p̄riā pena diluat. Dñc. z. j. Per. ij. In b̄ vocati
 est̄ charissimi qz ⁊ xps passus ē p̄ nob̄ u. rec̄.
 ut sic. uel. et. Secūdo rōne. Nā ut d̄t Bern. sup
 L̄an. ser. vñ. Xpiānū nomē a xpo deriuat ut ip̄m
 imit̄et. Et Aug⁹. de uita xpiana dicit̄. Nō in b̄ nob
 nōc̄m̄ q̄ xpiani dicimur blādiamur. sed. p̄r̄ b̄
 era nos iudicādos credam⁹ si nōb nomen fru
 stra uēdicim⁹. alēuū. Sed qm̄ xpm̄ oportuit pa
 ti crucē ⁊ ita tirare i gl̄iam suā. q̄ multo for̄m̄ ip̄ia
 nū uirtutem gl̄iaz nō suā sed xpi. oportet pati cru
 cē. sic ait Bern. Nam ut d̄t. j. q. ii. Sacerdos
 Est. q. ii. Charitātē. Iustus est. vñ illi soli p̄sc̄nt̄
 s̄p̄ d̄dū. f̄clitātē ⁊ q̄d̄ ip̄ d̄dū laboris ob̄
 sequiū. Terno exēplo ut similitudine. Et p̄mo exē
 plo thcologetico. Nā uidemus aliq̄s fideles nō

t̄m̄ q̄ fide sola sequunt̄ xpm̄ sed ope imitant̄ d̄
 abolū. de q̄b⁹ L̄m̄. ij. Lōt̄er̄t̄ se nolle deū ⁊c. fa
 cis aut̄ negant. S̄z q̄ uilitas i b̄: cū ut Jac. ij. d̄t
 fides sine op̄ib⁹ mortua ē. J̄s. Quid p̄dest q̄
 fide uigimur deo ⁊ op̄ib⁹ diuiniūm. Unq̄ b̄
 ut dicit̄ Bern. Ad cūmūlū inq̄ n̄re dānātois est
 fides n̄ra si nō fm̄ ea opamur. Alios xpianōs nō
 uimus q̄ sequunt̄ xpo: q̄ p̄formant̄ fide ⁊ opere
 sed ad xps. qz nō p̄ferat̄ sed in p̄cā recidunt
 Et qd̄ de talib⁹. Audiant̄ Petri. ij. canonica. ij.
 Facta sūt illis (inq̄) posteriora detentio ⁊ poib⁹.
 Lōt̄ḡ em̄ eis illud p̄uerbium. Lanis reuerſus
 ad uomitū ⁊ sus loca in uolubrazo lun. Hec ille
 Leo papa. Nō inchoāto sed p̄ferat̄ dabit̄
 p̄m̄ū. Dicit̄ q̄ cū Aug. oib⁹ ep̄colis. q̄ q̄ n̄ labo
 rabit̄ in semie nō gaudēbit̄ in messe: qm̄ dicente
 ap̄to. Que semiat b̄s bec ⁊ meret. l. p̄ p̄cā ignem
 cētū ⁊ p̄ p̄nia regnū celoz. Secūdo idē onidit̄ exē
 plo p̄p̄firo. Nā ap̄s p̄ suo rege mozi parat̄ fi
 ce. si q̄ offendit̄ rege. p̄rio acule se mo: de co
 rā rege: ut ait Amb. in b̄ca. q̄no maḡ rōnal̄
 o offendēs creator debet p̄nias agere. Terno exē
 plo polinico. Ut em̄ daret̄ p̄cipue qz fert̄ de maḡ
 Alexander q̄ p̄ ip̄o milites mozi pati erāt. Nam
 ipse Alexander cū pauc̄ militib⁹ mozi ad uerſari
 ozi dicit̄ adeo q̄ Dan̄ret̄ cū missis illi d̄ n̄
 dios plures saccos plenos papauoz grānis di
 q̄ in tācopioſa mltitudine ueniret̄ illū. Alexan
 der remisit̄ sibi sacculū vñū pleni pipib⁹ di. q̄ si
 cur paucais pipēz cōdireb⁹ lapozē m̄p̄oz pas
 pauēz. sic pauci milites Alexanderi multoz ml̄ti
 tudine exeret̄. Darij b̄ ideo. qz milites Alexātri
 pati erāt mozi. p̄ suo rege dñi uidebant̄ acē p̄mo
 inuadēt̄ ip̄e p̄m̄ij. q̄ ceter⁹ mlto maḡ debemus
 nos p̄ xpo ⁊c. l. Sed qm̄ qm̄ xpian⁹ debet
 exēplo b̄i Andree assimilari xpo i cruce sic p̄nic
 Rh̄dēt̄ q̄ sic crux b̄i Andree sūt crux xpi passi
 onis s̄lta papue i qn̄qz: sic ⁊ crux p̄nic debet
 assilari xpo ut p̄formet̄ panamur in qn̄qz p̄cipu
 is fm̄ nūez. qn̄qz uulnēz xpi p̄ gratiatiōe.

- Primo in patiendo inno center.
 - Secundo amanter.
 - Terno cōdonanter.
 - Quarto p̄ferant̄.
 - Quinto humiliter.
- Pr̄mo inno cent. Sic em̄ xps dñs inno cēs passus
 est. Et p̄ s̄q̄ pars q̄ in sinistra manu uuln⁹ iusce
 pit ⁊ in p̄ccatū in celo referuabit⁹? referuatiōez
 ut significet q̄ nulli vnq̄z sinistre nocuit. et m̄ ut
 agn⁹ ad occasiōē inno cēs dicit̄ et Esa. liij. Sic ⁊
 Andreas passus ē inno cent⁹ ut testabat̄ ois ip̄s
 di. Inno cēs hui⁹ sanguis sine cā damnat̄. Ita ⁊
 xpian⁹ debet sic p̄nic crucē pati ut de celo nō pec
 cet sed uiuat inno cēt̄. J̄s. J̄r̄ros est ⁊ nō p̄
 nitēs q̄ adducit̄ qd̄ penit̄. Nā p̄nia est p̄nitiā
 mala plāgere ⁊ plāgēda nō cōmittere. de pe. di. ij.
 S. j. Secūdo amāter. Un̄ sic. p̄ s̄q̄ pars cor uulnē
 ratiū fuare uoluit ⁊ uoluntariē c̄ passus ⁊ d̄ d̄ d̄

Solum I.

Generatioz generatio laudabit opera tua
 ⁊ potentiam tuam pronuntiabunt. scribitur. ps. cxiij. Cum non sine multa di-
 ligentia: sanctorum patrum studia: temporum decursus suppartant. non debi-
 tum quum magna utilitas ecclesiastico viris. ⁊ precipue illis qui ecclesiasticam po-
 litiam gubernare habent inde pronuntiat: nec vili statui bonorum hoc parum potest credere/
 dum est si temporaria mente ad rerum gestarum historiam: quas ob diuinam memoriam studiosi
 vti conscripserunt oculis leuati: quasi plerique id minus perspexerunt. Deceat namque viros virtu-
 ofum precedentium sacra sepe ad memoriam reuocare: vt bonis exemplis discant digno opero
 insistere. vt in malis valeant perditionis scopulum declinare. Verum nisi pcciosum a vili sepa-
 retur: stulta concupiscentia se tempore non valens: in tenebrarum vocaginem precipit cursu
 mergetur. Ob hoc sancti doctores videntes: qd ad intellectum sacrarum scripturarum ⁊ eccle-
 regimen: historiarum decursus et parte necessarius esset. simulqz omnium gestarum congerio in o-
 unilo. tum pro sui magnitudine tum pro superfluitate ⁊ vilitate factorum repetitione superflua
 cta qualdam nobis historiam cum onizantur amputatis fabulis superfluis ac generalis in
 terminatio que ad rem non pertinent. Sicqz factus est p maximos eorum labores: vt penes simi-
 lita temporum vtilitas brevissimo studio a quolibet intelligente iam ncedum sine labore: immo
 cum coaduo oblectatione possit incorporari. Deicit quoqz ad ornatum scripture: vt hoc pulchri-
 tudine non careat que omnibus gentibus tamqz lucerna psculda in obliquo loco prospeda
 fuit. Ingenium in super humanum quod magnifice plura compehendere facilius potest: hoc
 delicioso pccio dicitur totum florem penari non debuit. in quo varia virtutum exempla reprom-
 factaqz reproba eoz consideres: illa carere bec pcciterie moneretur. Videre enim supra modum
 est delectabile: qualiter patrum nostri parentis: ex quibus originem dicitur in situum fuisse: a si-
 mo omnium gubernatore deo: vnde quis decursus eorum: que modo defecti ⁊ profectura non
 bilis creatura in sapientia. virtute. potentia. sanctitate. longuitate. ⁊ sic de alijs. ⁊ in omnibus
 diuinum regimen admirari qd sic deus mirabilis in creaturis suis: qd nra mē admistrare ecclia/
 rum tu dicitur abissus. Deet infimisa alia per uolans humana industra penna quibusdam
 tuerne contemplationis: non solum pcciteria ⁊ pcciteria: sed etiam futura mentur: dum ex simili-
 bus ad similita progreditur. cui si bona voluntas adiuncta fuerit: tedio quodam incolatus hu-
 ius in dei surgit ad laudandum ⁊ regnandum: ⁊ contemplandum: cupiens dissolui: esse cu-
 cobito in eternum. Incipit ergo bec contemplatio i locida contemplatione creaturarum. ⁊ si-
 nit in feliciori tedio caridē: ⁊ appetitu creatoz. iuxta illud. ps. Quid enim mihi est in celo: ⁊ a te
 quid volui super terram. Vbi autem ad herere deo bonum est. Doc forte in pccallum: ⁊ verbo
 idem psalmista nobis persuadere nititur: dicens. Generatio ⁊ generatio laudabit opera tua: po-
 tentiam tuam pronuntiabunt. Quasi dicat. Per omnia que in mundo casura certumtu: ad te qd
 nra deficit sedere debem? Que vnaqz sententia valde accommoda est ad propositum nestrū. **E**nim
 enim teste augustino plura in sacra scriptura commemorantur que nibi significant. ⁊ tamen ne-
 cessaria sunt propter ea que aliquid significant necesse est talibus itari: quasi sterilia sunt sic illa
 que secunda deuotione immediate in deum mentem nostram subtrouit. alicui non recte scd
 ruram legimus in qua spiritus sanctus loqui credendus est. Sunt ergo arida quo ad superficiali-
 litere: sed graua quo ad spirituale intelligendam. Que autem ita aliena sunt: vt nequaquam spiri-
 tualiter intelligi possunt. aut non expedit omni tamen veneratione digna sunt propter suam in-
 quem ordinantur: qui est scire ⁊ diligere deum. Et de hoc genere videtur esse supputatio annorum
 que in sacra historia diligentissime annotata continetur. De qua: vt idem Augustinus testatur
 hoc certissime tenendum est q tanta est diuina auctoritate robotata: vt oino falsissimū sit: qd qd
 ab ea discrepat: vt cū ea omnino concordari nō possit. Quocum ita sint: itū valde videtur: cur
 sancte scripture tractatores de hac materia in tantum sunt diuersi in pluri locis vqz bedie. vt
 aut omnino aut vt nequean t concordari. Et redit illa antiqua ⁊ famosa questio de translatione
 lex. in perpetuum: an potius ei standum sit in supputatione annorum: an textu debitorum: quez

XVII. 717J Rolewinck, Werner Rolewinck 1425-1502

Fasciculus Te[m]por[um] Omnes Antiquorum Cronicas Complecte[n]s.

[Strassburg: Johann Pruss, not before
1490.], \$16,000

Folio 28 x 20cm. $\pi^6, A-O^8, p^4$. 17 different wood cuts (of 25). Bound in a half vellum over raised bands. Rubricated throughout. This is beautiful and rare illustrated incunabulum.

The Fasciculus temporum is one of the most famous chronicle in the history of the world: the invention of printing is also mentioned. Fol lxxxix v. This title has the distinction of being one of only a few books printed in this period while the author still lived. At least thirty editions were printed between the editio princeps (1474) and the death of Rolewinck. Five of these editions were printed Johan Pruss, four in Latin, as is the present edition, and one in German.

This edition is expanded from the first to include events which occurred since the first edition, such as the death of Mathias Corvinus, King of Hungary in 1490. As well as many descriptions of strange occurrences, monstrous births and earthquakes, comets, the Strange miracle of St Gengulphus. (Gangulphus' relics were translated to Varennes-sur-Aumance in the diocese of Langres, where his cult developed, and later distributed to various places in France, Germany, the Low Countries and Switzerland.) ... et c.

Solium. III.

Nota fm doctores debita pena h tpe mudo inflicta. Qd ei luxuria abudaunt que corpora polluit. ideo p aqua ter- raloza z mūdā fuit. In fine at mudi qz cupiditas abun- dabit per ignē exuret. Lux enī z argēū ignē purgari solent.

Doc signū federis qđ do inter me et vos. z ad oēū aiām. gen. ix.

Archa noe habit in logitudine. ccc. cubitos. in latitudine. l. cubitos. z in altitudine. xxx. z in immittate. i. cubitū. gen. vi.

CCCCXXXVII CCCCCCLIII II CCCCXLII

tonus illius noe

Tempus diluuij

Die matrisale sensum? quo ad multitudinem ānoz omniū qđ scriptura commemorat. An ei d. ānos haberet. dixit ei dñs. **E**difica domū sū vīā. qm adhuc. d. ānis v. ucs. rudi. Propter tā. illū rps nō edificabo domū. z s' arboribz circa vepes doimūt. vi prius consuatur

Lamech cū iam sensuier z caligassent octi ep'a p'u- tro ducbat. qui putans q' serā vidisset. indicant ei vt sagittaret. z sic ip'uz caym transfixit. **Q**u' ob h' p'uez verbis adcoā sūū' sū' viciaz morderetur

Hoe vici' iustus grām inuenit / tam domino. Cum enim esset annorum. d. genuit sem chamz iaphet. Arca de mādato dñi edifi- care cepit. camqz in. c. annis p'fecit. **E**t primo ergo āno iā archa p'pleta itez dñs apparuit ei. man- dans vt cū vore sua z filijs. corūqz v'coibz archā intraret. z cū animalibz. z cū statim diluuiū inunda- uit. **S**entiatqz aqua super altissimos montes cubitis. xv. gen. vij. **E**t nota q' eodē die dñico t'ma- ro in quo ingressus fuit. āno reuoluto cū vniuersis que ibi erāt egressus est. **P**ost diluuiū acci- dir ipsi noe illa famosa ebrietas. cuius occasione ipse filijs. i. sem z iaphet p' honore paterno z bo- necia verē dīa bñdicit. filio vero sūo chā p' irrisōe z irreuēntia maledicit. **E**t h' fm aug' sū' p'i- ma mentio de seruitute. z per oppositū de nobilitate. **N**ec putā dñi est q' oēs de cham dēcēdentes fuerint ignobiles z impotentes. cum ipsi ceperūt p'mo ēē p'ōctes super terram. vt patēt de **F**lem- roth. z regibz chanaan z aff'oz zc. **H**ec oēs de sem z iaphet fuerūt virtuosissimi nobiles aut poten- tes cū pene omnes in ydolatriā crimen ceciderūt. z ab alijs opp'essi sepe fuerūt. sed hec maledictō z benedictio vicia z virtutes respicit. propter que vā quas homo veraciter dicitur nobilitas

The printing of this text was tricky. The page layout has a double-ruled strip in the middle of the page, separating the text above (Biblical history with commentary by the Church Fathers) from the text below (secular history). Within the strip are one, two or three circles containing the names of people, beginning with Adam. Dates above are calculated from the creation of the world (5199 B.C.) Dates below, printed upside down, indicate the number of years before the birth of Christ. The illustrations including a frontispiece on the verso of the half-title of a pilgrim, twelve town views, an Ark and rainbow, and a full-length portrait of Jesus Christ. A city in flames illustrates the destruction of Sodom and Gomorrah, Troy, and others. Three woodcuts illustrate omens, such as comets, eclipses and monstrous births. The page with the woodcut of Jesus Christ (fol. 37) is an example of sophisticated typesetting; the figure of Christ is surrounded on four corners by the names of the Evangelists with quotations from the Bible.

¶ Regarding the art (invention) of printing {P³}Rolewinck wrote: *“This is the art of arts, the science of sciences, through the swift practice of which the valuable treasures of wisdom and of knowledge, instinctively desired by all men, leap as it were from the deep shadows of their hiding places, and enrich and illuminate this world in its evil state. The unlimited virtue of books which formerly in Athens or Paris and the other schools or sacred libraries was made known to a very few students is now spread by this discovery to every tribe, people, nation, and language everywhere, a true fulfillment of Proverbs, ch. 1”*.

Goff R276 ; Hain-C. 6916; GW M38725; Schreiber, Manuel, 5119; Polain (B) 3362. See Stillwell.

367J Rosenheim, Petrus de Rosenheim. (1380-1432).

Incipit Roseum memoriale divinatorum eloquiorum

[Köln] : [Southern Germany : n.pr., about 1480-90?] or [Cologne? : n.pr., about 1483] or [Ludwig von Renchen?], 1483 Deutschlaand, ca. 1480. Price. \$13,500

Quarto 19 x 15.5 cm. (a-f⁸) a1 blank and lacking. First Edition. Text in one column, 32 lines. Type: 80G. Initials painted in red, rubricated in red ink throughout . First edition . ¶ Gothic script, rubricated, red and blue hand-painted initials, 92 unnumbered pages. A very good copy, old repair to the first blank leaf, a few spots, pale stain at the lower blank corner of the first quires. Rubricated and initials supplied in red and blue. First Edition. This copy is bound in a simple vellum binding from an antiphonal leaf. Gothic script, rubricated, red and blue.

¶ This is one of the earliest printed books on the **ars memorativa** or mnemotechnics this is the rare first edition of the Roseum memoriale composed by the German Benedictine monk Petrus of Rosenhaym (Upper Bavaria), written between 1423 and 1426 for Cardinal Giulio Branda di Castiglione. Petrus of Rosenhaym composed numerous treatises, sermons, and verses: the Roseum memoriale is surely his most famous work, enjoying wide popularity during the fifteenth century and first half of the sixteenth century.

¶ Each couplet commences with a different letter in the order of the alphabet (omitting K, X, Y, Z, but including vowel I). These letters correspond to the numbers that appear on the cuts, and together form a method of memorizing the events of the Scripture as told by each of the Evangelists. It is a poem composed of 1,194 verses followed by an epilogue of seventy-three hexameters, in which every chapter of the Bible (excluding the Psalms) is summed up in a distich. The mnemotechnic method here employed is extremely complex: the hexameters of each section of the summary form an acrostic of the letters of the alphabet. ¶ Based on Latin verses about Holy Scripture, it uses characteristic couplets (distiches) to express the main content of all chapters of the Old and New Testament.

¶ This was a highly popular and broadly used manual, its copies could be found in almost every European church after the invention of the printing press it was printed in several different locations. This early medieval incunable has not been clearly dated (This edition) researchers attribute it to the Upper Rhine region sometime between 1480 and 1483. . After 1423, he was appointed 'cursor biblicus' and 'magister studentium'.

Dated by Goff and IGI about 1483 "The edition is assigned by Proctor to the printer Ludwig von Renchen, active in Cologne from 1483 to ca. 1495, while ISTC gives Southern Germany between 1480-1490 and GW tentatively suggests Oberrhein, 1483.

ISTC ir00336000;

Goff R336; BMC I 312; ; GW M32724; Polain(B) 3128; IBE 4559; IGI 7668; IBP 4380; Sajó-Soltész 2676; Madsen 3549; Borm 2134; Hubay(Würzburg) 1704; AmBCat 199; Walsh 492; Oates 867; Pr 1517; BSB P-362; Van der Haegen II,2:16,4?; Young 278.

XIX. 300J. JOHANNES de SACRO BOSCO. (c. 1195 - c. 1256)

Figura sphere cu[m] glosis Georgii de Mo[n]teferrato artiu[m] [et] medici[n]e doctoris : gradiam [et] gloriam dabit dominus.

Venice: [Jacobus Pentius, de Leuco] for Georgius de Monteferrato 1500, die 28 ianuarii. 1500. \$11,000

Quarto. 21 x 16 cm. A-E⁴ F⁶. This copy is bound in full laced cased later vellum, blue edges, and recent marbled endpapers.

There is a large woodcut on title page 'sphaera mundi', see to the left and three other large woodcut diagrams in text.

Woodcut capitals, also spaces with guide-letters. Tear repaired in corner of f. 2, with some text loss.

This illustrated incunable is printed by Jacobus Pentius, de Leuce who started printing in 1495, his press was chiefly active after the turn of the century.

¶ In 1220 Sacrobosco wrote *Tractatus de Sphaera* a book on astronomy in four chapters. The first chapter deals with the shape and place of the Earth within a spherical universe. The second chapter deals with various circles on the sky. The third chapter describes rising and setting of heavenly bodies from different geographical locations while the fourth chapter gives a brief introduction to Ptolemy's theory of the planets and of eclipses.

This book, which predates Grosseteste's astronomy book, is well written and was widely used throughout Europe.

Goff J421; Klebs, A.C. *Incunabula scientifica et medica*,; entry 874.30; BMC V 566; HCR 14126; Essling 264; Sander 6668; Pell Ms 6718 (6683); Hillard 1153; Péligny 480; IGI 5353; Hubay(Augsburg) 1247; Pr 5705; GW M14661

United States of America. The Walters Art Museum Library, Library of Congress, New York Public Library, Huntington Library, Smithsonian Institution, Univ. of Chicago, Williams College.

XX. 440J Savonarola, Girolamo, 1452-1498

Incipit Expositio v[er]bi De
ditatio s[er]m[on]is Hieronimi sauo-
narole de Ferraria ordiis p[ro]p[ri]o
caro[rum] in psalmu[m] In te d[omi]ne
speraui. qua[m] i[n] vltimis dieb[us]
d[omi]ni vite sue sine p[re]iolaretur
edidit.

Tristicia obsedit me
magno et forti exer-
citu vallauit me. oc-
cupauit cor meum cla-
morib[us] et armis die noctuq[ue]
contra me pugnare non cessat.
Amici mei sunt in castris eius
et facti sunt mihi inimici. Que-
cuius video non cuius audio. ver-
um illa tristitia d[omi]ni ferunt memoria
amicorum meorum contristat. recor-
dacio filiorum me affligit consi-
deracio claustrorum celle me an-
git. Meditacio studiorum me-
orum dolore me afficit. cogita-
cio peccatorum me premittit. Sicut
enim febre laborantibus oia dul-
cia amara videtur ita mihi oia
in merore et tristitiam conuer-
tuntur. Magnu[m] profecto onus su-
per cor tristitia hec. Venen-
tu[m] aspidu[m] pestifera p[er]niciosa mur-
murat contra deum. blasphemam
re non cessat. ad desperationem
horrat. Infelix ego homo. quomodo
me de manibus eius sacrilegis
liberabit. Si oia quod video et au-
dio verilla sequuntur et fortis est
me pugnans. quis erit pre-
torum meus. Quis auxiliabit
mihi. Quo vadis. quod pacto effu-
gia. Scio quod facias. Ad inuisi-
bilia me percertas et adducas ca-

stra visibilia. Et quis erit d[omi]ni
ta excelsi r[ati]o et tribulatio exercit[us].
Spes que d[omi]ni iustitiam est. spes
inquit contra tristitiam veniet et ex-
pugnabit eam. Quis stare pos-
serit in spem. Audi quid dicit
propheta. Tu es d[omi]ne spes mea
altissimum posuisti refugium tu-
um. Quis stabit contra doim.
quod expugnare poterit refugium
eius quod est altissimum. Vocabo
itaque eam veit profecto nec me
confundet. Ecce iam veit gaudia
attulit pugnare me docuit
dixitque mihi. Clama ne ces-
ses et aio. Quid clamo dicin-
quit confidens et ex toto corde.

In te d[omi]ne
speraui non
confundar in eter-
num in iusticia tu-
a libera me.

O mira potentia spiritus cuius fa-
ctus non potuit tollerare tristi-
cia. Ia veit consolacio. Clamer
et obstreper nunc tristitia cui ex-
ercitu suo. Premat mundum in
surgant hostes. nihil timeo
quam in te d[omi]ne sperant. quam tu es
spes mea. quam tu altissimum
posuisti refugium tuum. Ia ip[s]um
ingressus sum spes me intro-
duxit. non ego ipsud fecerit intra-
ui. ipsa me excusabit coram te.

a i

Incipit Expositio v[e]l Meditacio f[rat]ris Hieronimi sauonarole de Ferraria ordi[ni]s p[rae]dicatorum in psalmu[m] In te d[omi]ne speraui. qua[m] i[n] vltimis dieb[us] du[m] vite sue fine[m] prestolaretur edidit.

Magdenburg: Moritz Brandis, 1500. Price: \$6,600.

Second Edition. Quarto 20 x 15 cm. a⁴,b⁴. (8) lvs., rubricated in red, modern boards.[*] - First leaf w. incipit with outer remargined ; a few tiny wormholes throughout (mostly in blank margins). Savonarola writes at the last bit written, a quite heartfelt passage""BURN away Thy face from my sins, and blot out all thine iniquities. Wherefore, Lord, regardest Thou my sins ? Why numberest Thou them ? Why considerest Thou them so diligently ? Knowest Thou not that man is as a flower of the field ? Wherefore lookest Thou not rather on the face of Thy Christ ? Alas, wretch that I am, why see I Thee angry withme ? I confess I have sinned, but do Thou in Thy goodness have mercy upon me : turn away Thy face from my sins. Thy face is Thy knowledge ; turn away therefore Thy knowledge from my sins. I mean not that knowledge which consists in simple apprehension, wherewith Thou seest all things at all times, but the knowledge which consists in approval and disapproval, whereby Thou dost approve the actions of the just, and by disapproving dost condemn the sins of the wicked. Take not such knowledge of my sins as to impute them to me ; but turn away Thy face from my sins, that through Thy mercy they may be blotted out. Regard, Lord, the soul which Thou hast created, regard Thy likeness which Thou hast formed. For Thou didst create it in Thine image, and I poor wretch have overlaid it with the likeness of the devil." (Translated by Perowne.)

Under torture Savonarola confessed to having invented his prophecies and visions, then recanted, then confessed again. In his prison cell in the tower of the government palace he composed meditations on Psalms 51 and 31. On the morning of 23 May 1498, Savonarola and two other friars were led out into the main square where, before a tribunal of high clerics and government officials, they were condemned as heretics and schismatics, and sentenced to die forthwith. Stripped of their Dominican garments in ritual degradation, they mounted the scaffold in their thin white shirts. Each on a separate gallows, they were hanged, while fires were ignited below them to consume their bodies. To prevent devotees from searching for relics, their ashes were carted away and scattered in the Arno. Scapecchi, P. Cat. Savonarola,; 87 (Catalogo delle edizioni di Girolamo Savonarola (secc. XV-XVI) possedute dalla Biblioteca nazionale centrale di Firenze) Girolamo Savonarola, Prison Meditations on Psalms 51 and 31 Tr., Ed. John Patrick Donnelly S.J. (Milwaukee, Marquette University Press, 1994).

Hieronymus Savonarola (1452-1498) In te Domine speravi. The Dominican preacher wrote this text while in prison in Florence in 1498, charged with heresy, and having been

found guilty was burned at the stake in that year. He was a Catholic and a critic of the luxurious lives of the rulers, the Medici family, of the Florentian people and the corruption in the Catholic Church. His sermons resulted in the downfall of the ruling Medici family. Pope Alexander VI excommunicated him.IMG_5919.jpeg " Savonarola , after his first " examination " nearly a month of quiet in the little prison , which, after all, was not less spacious or comfortable than his cell. This resting time the victim employed in a manner befitting his character and life. He wrote two meditations , one on the Miserere (5 1st Psalm) and the other on the 31 st Psalm, in which he poured out his whole heart in communion with God. With the right hand which had been spared to him in diabolical mercy that he might be able to sign the false papers which were intended to cover him with ignominy, he still had it in his power to leave a record of that intercourse with his heavenly Master in which his stricken soul found strength and comfort. Between the miserable lies of the notary Ceccone, over which those Florentine nobles in the palace were wrangling ; and the stillness of the little prison hung high in air over their heads, where a great soul in noble trust and sadness approached its Maker, what a difference!"

Goff (suppl.); S-206a; BMC 15th cent.; II 601; GW M40482 ; Hain-Copinger; 14412; Reichling; 1384; Audin de Rians, E. Bib.; 138; ISTC No. is00206500.
<https://data.cerl.org/istc/is00206500> United Kingdom British Library (IA.10973) United States of America. Yale add ??? US, TX SMU. Item #804

et fieri. qz q̄ cepit te diligere
et bñficijs ḡc̄sqz ad suū ad/
rem puocare. nō deficiet sed
maḡ perficiet opus suū que
naz causa naturalis incipit
opus vt in medio trinceris de
sistat. **V**irtus semis nō cessat
donec fruct⁹ ad p̄fectionē p̄
ducatur. q̄ quis reliq̄t pullos
suos anteq̄ seip̄os regere va
leant. **E**t hoc faciūt. q̄ vtili
tas ex hoc puenit illis. nulla
p̄fectio s̄ t̄m labor. **A**mor igit̄
tur cogit causas naturales
suos effectos ad p̄fectū pdu
cere. **H**ortas cōpellit eas quā
cupiūt diffundere. bonū est. n.
sui p̄p̄ius diffusiuū si b̄ faciūt
creaturē. **Q**uid faciet creator
Ipsē enī amor est ip̄e boitas
infinita. **A**n nō p̄ficiet opus
suū. **B**udidm̄ ihm̄. **M**ea in
quit volūtas est vt faciā vo
luntatē ei⁹ q̄ misit me vt p̄fi
ciā opus eius. **Q**ui igit̄ cepit
te amare suis bñficijs et gra
tije attrahere te a peccis mun
dare. p̄culdubio p̄ficiet opus
suū. hec enī s̄t p̄paraciones
eterne vite. **E**t igit̄ nūc ca
dēs nō est collisus. **N**ōne qz
dñs sup̄posuit manū suā et q̄
re sup̄posuit manū suā. q̄re
cōuertit ad se cor tuū. **E**t te
ad penitentiā puocauit. **E**t te
consolatus est te. **N**ōne vt te
mundet ⁊ ḡa sua dignū faci
at et ad eternā vitam pducat.
Nō sunt hec illusiones aut
imagiaciones tue s̄ diuine in/

spiraciones s̄ esto imagiaciones
sūt. nōne bone sunt. nōne de
fidei frute. pueniūt. **E**t itaqz
oē bonū a deo sit. vtiqz sunt
he imagiaciones diuine illūta
ciones. **E**xulta ḡ in sb̄tis istis.
Ad hec ḡba adco cōfortatū ē
cor meū q̄ p̄ gaudio psallere
incepti dices. **D**omin⁹ illūta
cio mea. et sal⁹ mea que time
bo. **D**ñs p̄ccator vite mee a q̄
trepidabo. ⁊ ad pedes dñi cū
lacris puolurus dixi. **D**omi
ne si consistant aduersus me
castra non timebit cor meus.
Quā fortitudo mea ⁊ refugiu
meū es tu et p̄pter nomē tuū
deduces me et enutries me.

Ex p̄licite expositio v̄. **M**e
ditacio s̄tis. **N**icronimi. **S**a
nonarole. **F**errariensis. **S**acri
ordinis. **P**reicator. in psalmū
In te dñe speraui. ⁊c. quam
morte p̄uentus explete nō
potuit.

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XXI. 235J Tygrinus or Nicolaus Tegrinus or Tegrini

Lucensium Oratio Luculentissima Pont. Maximo Alexandro Sexto per Nicolaum Tygrinu[m] Lucensem Vtriusq[ue] Iuris.

Rome: [Andreas Freitag], 15 October 1492. Price \$4,000

Quarto 20 x 13 cm: A⁴ First edition (see below). Bound in a vellum leaf printed by Jenson 1497. Ex-libris Walter Goldwater.

Oration such as this are usually rare and short this one is both it is a tribute from the City of Lucca to the election of Pope Alexander VI. This is one of three almost simultaneously published prints of this on October 25, 1492 before the newly elected Borgia Pope Alexander VI. held this speech. – ""This was the typical 'Oratio' - in the style of the times, both florid and unctous - which extolled the virtues of the Pope, traits which subsequent events failed to confirm!"" (Bühler) According to Bühler's study, The Freitag printing was preceded by the editions of Stephan Planck (in Roman type), whose corrections Freitag employed in his edition."

CF Bühler, The Earliest Editions of the ""Oratio"" (1492) by Nicolaus Tygrinus (in: Gutenberg JB 1975, pp. 97-99)"

Goff T563; HC 15751*; Pell Ms 10972; CIBN T-51; Nice 209; IGI 9670; IBE 5542; BMC IV 137;

United States of America
The Walters Art Museum, Bryn
Mawr College, Library of
Congress,
New York, Columbia
University, Huntington
Library
Southern Methodist Univ,
Southern Methodist
Univ., Yale

Andreas Freitag and most of the of other Roman printers of note, Have German names which might indicate German birth and education. This conclusion is warranted by their occasional use of Gothic types for devotional books of inferior size. A few unnamed Italians were connected with these early printing houses, but mainly as patrons or money-lenders. They did not desire to have their names appear as partners. Freitag printed one book at Gaeta dated 1487, then he turns up in Rome in 1492 and seems to have been still printing 1495.

XXII. 246] Gerardus de Zutphania (1367-1398)

[De spiritualibus ascensionibus.] Tractatus de spiritualibus ascensionibus Add: David de Augusta: De exterioris et interioris hominis compositione Lib. II. 1 (De quatuor in quibus incipientes deo servire debent esse cauti)

Basel : Johann Amerbach and Johann Petri de Langendorff, not after 1489].

\$4,000

Octavo 20 x13 cm. Lacking a¹ (blank) & a² title. Rubricated in red, initials painted in red, blue and green. Contemporary binding in full calf, with blind tool. Zerbolt was born in 1367 into a wealthy burgher family in Zutphen, then in the Duchy of Guelders. He was first education in his hometown, and after attending one or more Latin schools elsewhere, between 1383 and 1385 he joined the Brothers of the Common Life's at St. Lebwin school in nearby Deventer.

¶ Even in the Brothers of the Common Life's community of "plain living and high thinking" Gerard was remarkable for his absorption in the sacred sciences and his utter oblivion of all matters of merely earthly interest. He held the office of librarian, and his deep learning in moral theology and canon law did the brothers good service, in helping them to meet the prejudice and opposition which their manner of life at first aroused.

¶ This is the inaugural treatise by Gerard Zerbolt of Zütphen, described by Post (in "The Modern Devotion") as "the most fertile and the most successful writer the Brothers [of the Common Life] ever produced." (Cath. Ency.)

In June 1398, the plague drove most of the Brethren, including Zerbolt, from Deventer. They found refuge in Amersfoort until November. Here the legality of the Brotherhood was attacked regularly by the local clergy. Soon after his return to Deventer, Zerbolt traveled to the Benedictine monastery at Dikninge in Drente to confer with its learned abbot Arnold about the attacks. On his way home on December 3, Zerbolt and his companion stopped for the night at Windesheim, a small village just south of Zwolle. He felt mortally ill and died within a few hours, at the age of 31. Because of his heralded status, the Windesheim canons buried him quickly in an honored spot in their own chapel, before the Brethren from Deventer could collect the body.

¶ This work of mystic theology was a major influence upon Saint Ignatius Lyola and the founding of the Jesuits Here, Zerbolt outlines how one can redeem the soul from its fallen state, moving to higher and higher levels through "self-knowledge, repentance, combat of sin, mortification, the practice of humility and obedience." (Post)

The "Devotio Moderna" helped pave the way for the religious reform movements of the 15th and 16th centuries, in particular with its emphasis on the importance of every person developing a personal relationship with God, as Zerbolt details here.

According to Pollard, our printer Amerbach (1430-1513) issued his first book from a Basel establishment in 1478, and in his career printed about 100 incunabula.

Herbermann, Charles, ed. (1913). ""'. Catholic Encyclopedia.

The Spiritual Ascent: A Devotional Treatise by Zerbolt, Gerard, 1367-1398; Thomas, à Kempis, ca. 1380-1471. G. H. Gerrits "Inter Timorem Et Spem: A Study of the Theological Thought of Gerard Zerbolt", BRILL publisher, 1986. Marguerin de la Bigne, Bibliotheca Patrum, XXVI. >Karl Ullmann, Reformatoren vor der Reformation; and K. Hirsche in Herzog's Realencyklopädie, 2nd ed. Material Evidence in Incunabula,; 02019755

¶ Goff,; G177;ISTC,; ig00177000; Oates,; 2803; Bod-inc,; G-081; Pr,; 7638; BMC,; III:752; BSB-Ink,; G-127; GW,; 10689

United States of America:

Boston Public, Bryn Mawr, Free Library of Philadelphia, Library of Congress, Ohio State, Huntington (2), Newberry, Univ. of Houston, Yale (2)

Hinc de ascensionib⁹ q̄b⁹ ascēdere et redire
 debeas / restat s̄b̄iequit̄ dicere. Audisti autē
 pri⁹ q̄ trib⁹ descensionib⁹ q̄si trib⁹ locūsimus
 dietis a loco in quo te dñs poluit recessisti: ita nihil
 omnī tribus ascensionib⁹ illuc necesse ē te redire.
 Prima autē ascētio ip̄a ē q̄ ascendis itē ad cor tuū.
 Nege enī egressus es a corde tuo p̄ peccata. nec po-
 res spūali exercitio i corde p̄ficere nisi fideas ad cor.
 S̄c̄da p̄p̄ta adiminet. Redire p̄uaticatores ad cor.
 S̄c̄da ascētio cū iā ad cor redieris: ascendas de cor-
 de ip̄uro p̄ concupiscentias ad cor purū: et hinc i ascē-
 sio ē puritas cordis et caritas: et trāsit p̄ sc̄m̄ desen-
 tendis p̄ inordinatas affectiōes inatas ab 2da vel
 priūa multas a tempo / et hec p̄ncipal⁹ ordinari pot̄ p̄
 priūū descēnū.

Ube prima ascēsiōe cōtra peccatū mor-
 tale: et de tribus gradib⁹ hu⁹ ascēsiōis: et
 de cōmisiōe. *Cap. xij.*

Uincigit surge et sursum ascēde: incipe ad cor
 tuū p̄gere. Sicut autē peccatū mortale tri-
 pliciter descensū cōpleuisti. Itaq̄ auertus es a
 creatore tuo p̄ supbia in qua ē formalis rō p̄ci: con-
 uertus es ad creaturā p̄ delectandem: ac deinde per
 opandos p̄ legē diuinā de tui trāgress⁹ es p̄ceptū.
 Ita trib⁹ gradib⁹ oportet te cōuatio ascēdere. Nō
 vt auertas cor tuū a creaturis et a patris: et habeas
 quādam cordis firmā auertsiōē: et firmū q̄dā p̄po-
 sitū deo tuo seruicā / et nisi q̄ te creaturis p̄ illicitam

delectationē sub iudiciū: etiā si misse moribus mori
 te oportet. Itō cō autē in genere debes p̄ponere: nō
 autē sup hoc singulari te examinare: solebis inuol-
 tutū q̄ tantū a deo tuo recessisti: q̄ tantū eū offendidisti /
 et q̄dā mō iterū crucifixisti. Ecce talis auertsiō ip̄a est
 vna ascētio / cui⁹ nomē ē cōrro q̄ cor tuū q̄dā mō a
 sua duritia frangit. Sicut enī in naturalib⁹ res dure
 dicuntur conterī: cū in partes minutas frangunt. vel
 minuit: ita methaphorice cor dicitur conterī: q̄m̄ ip̄m
 a sua duritia emollit q̄d prius auertit a deo durū et
 obfirmatū fuit i peccatis: nō cedens diuine iustitiā /
 nō admittens iunctū spūsancti: s̄ obdurans: autē
 ne audiret. Sed cor durū s̄m̄ Bernardum. j. de con-
 sideratione dicit: q̄ nec copunctione scādit / nec pi-
 etate molliuit / nec mouet precibus ec̄. Cōteritur
 autem quando tam liquefit compunctiōe et emollit
 pietate.

Ube confessione que est secundus gra-
 dus huius ascensionis. *Capitulum xij.*

Quia nō in p̄cis tuis deū p̄ supbia cōtēp-
 sisti: nō necesse ē vt te homini dei vicario cla-
 ues habeant humiliter subdas vice dei / et et
 itaq̄ ip̄o vno iudici tuo assistēs hūilit̄ et p̄rite et do-
 lole peccata tua confitearis. Humiliter videlicet
 te in omnibus accusas / et p̄p̄tia peccata agnosces /
 in moribus / in gestis / in prolatione verborum / in re-
 spōsiōib⁹ / singularib⁹ alijs tanq̄ iudici tuo assistens
 te habetas. Laue ne vt qdā maḡs cōmū p̄fiteris idē q̄
 ras laudari vti a deo merer̄ p̄probari. Sic humilit̄ q̄
 b 4